
Best-Practice guide JUGENE

Florian Janetzko, FZJ

Gilles Civario, ICHEC

Maciej Cytowski, ICM

Maciej Szpindler, ICM

Stefanie Janetzko, FZJ

Alexander Schnurpfeil, FZJ

Brian Wylie, FZJ

Huub Stoffers, SARA

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1. Introduction

The IBM Blue Gene/P system JUGENE (Jülich Blue Gene/P) is hosted by the Gauss Centre for Supercomputing (GCS) at the Forschungszentrum Jülich (FZJ) in Germany. It was installed as a 16 rack system in October 2007 and was No. 2 in the Top500 in November 2007. It was one of the prototype systems in the PRACE Preparatory Phase project. After an upgrade to a 72 rack system in 2009 JUGENE became Europe's first Peta-FLOP/s supercomputer and starting on July 1, 2010 JUGENE was the first Tier-0 system available in the PRACE project for successful PRACE resource applications.

Figure 1. IBM Blue Gene/P JUGENE hosted by Forschungszentrum Jülich.

This best practice guide provides information about JUGENE in order to enable users of the system to achieve good performance of their applications. The guide covers a wide range of topics from the detailed description of the hardware through information about the basic production environment including how to login and the accounting procedure as well as information about porting and submitting jobs, up to tools and strategies how to analyze and improve the performance of applications.

Information about JUGENE is available online:

User information, Software, FAQs [http://www.fz-juelich.de/ias/jsc/EN/Expertise/Supercomputers/JUGENE/JUGENE_node.html]

Message of the day for JUGENE [http://www2.fz-juelich.de/jsc/CompServ/services/high_msg.html#bgp]

2. System Architecture and Configuration

The Blue Gene/P has a massively parallel supercomputer architecture with different types of nodes and networks. In total JUGENE has 72 racks and contains 73,728 compute nodes or 294,912 cores.

This section describes the specific hardware and the configuration of the Blue Gene/P JUGENE from the processor architecture through the different networks to the files systems which are available. Much of the information in this section is taken from the “Redbook: IBM System Blue Gene Solution: Blue Gene/p Application Development ” RedBook AD.

2.1. Processor architecture

JUGENE has four types of nodes with partly different hardware and software characteristics. There are two different processor architectures used in the different nodes.

Login nodes and *service nodes* of JUGENE contain IBM 64-bit Power6 processors (p6 550) with 4.2 GHz.

The microprocessor of JUGENE's *compute nodes* and *I/O nodes* is a PowerPC 450, Book E compliant, 32-bit microprocessor with a clock speed of 850 MHz. The PowerPC 450 microprocessor, with double-precision floating-point multiply add unit (double FPU), can deliver four floating-point operations per cycle with 3.4 Giga-FLOP/s per core.

2.2. Building blocks

The Blue Gene/P system contains the following components: chip, compute card, node card, rack. These building blocks are illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Building blocks (chip, compute card, node card and rack) of the JUGENE system

2.2.1. Chip

The Blue Gene/P processor chip contains four PowerPC 450 cores (quad-core chip) where each core has a double-precision floating-point multiply add unit (double FPU). The processor chip has a peak performance of 13.6 GFLOP/s. It is sometimes referred to as *node*. Each core has 64 kB private L1 cache (32 kB data and 32 kB instruction cache) and an L2 prefetch cache of 14x256 bytes.

2.2.2. Compute card

The compute card contains the quad-core processor chip with 8 MB shared L3 cache, 2 GB of shared DDR2 SDRAM and connectors for different networks and for power supply. It is also referred to as a

compute node. Compute nodes have no local file system, they must route I/O operations to an external device via I/O nodes.

2.2.3. Node card

32 compute cards are collected into one *node card*. Up to two I/O cards can be added optionally. The node cards are air-cooled.

2.2.4. Rack

32 node cards are collected into one *rack*. Half a rack (16 node cards) is called a *midplane* and is the smallest building block for the TORUS network. One rack contains 1024 compute nodes or 4,096 cores.

2.2.5. Special nodes

As already mentioned, JUGENE possesses three further types of nodes besides the compute nodes which were described above. Two of these types are relevant for users:

- *I/O nodes*: The hardware is identical to the compute nodes. It is not possible to login neither to the compute nodes nor to the I/O nodes. The I/O nodes take care of the I/O to external devices (file systems). JUGENE possesses in total 600 I/O nodes. Details can be found in Section 2.6.1.
- *Login nodes*: JUGENE has two front-end or login nodes, each has eight Power6 cores (4.2 GHz) and 32 GB of memory.

2.3. Operating system

The JUGENE compute nodes run a lightweight, proprietary operating system referred to as the Compute Node Kernel (CNK). The CNK is a Linux-like 32 bit operating system supporting a large subset of Linux compatible system calls as well as threads and dynamic linking. The CNK redirects all of the file system load and network traffic to the I/O node. Thus, using the CNK provides very little interference with the applications that run on the compute nodes.

The I/O nodes provide access to external devices. All I/O requests are routed through these nodes. The nodes run an optimized version of the Linux operating system.

The login nodes (front-end nodes) provide the working environment for the users with a SuSE Linux (SLES 10, 64 bit) full-featured operating system.

2.4. Memory architecture

The Blue Gene/P system has a distributed-memory architecture which includes an on-chip cache hierarchy and an off-chip memory. It contains optimized on-chip symmetrical multiprocessing (SMP) support for locking and communication between the four processors (cores) of the compute node. The aggregate memory of the system is distributed without any hardware sharing between nodes. The total amount of physical memory per JUGENE compute node is 2 GB and the memory is laid out as a single, flat and fixed-sized virtual address space shared between the operating system kernel and the user application.

The first level (L1) cache is contained in the PowerPC 450 core. The PowerPC 450 L1 cache is 64-way set-associative. The automatic prefetching has been disabled for performance reasons. The cache-line size is 32 bytes.

Tip

- The usage of the FPUs (floating-point units) and FPU registers can be optimized using the XL compiler directives or assembler instructions.

- To benefit from the SIMD (single instruction multiple data) instructions, data must fit in the L1 cache.

The second level (L2R and L2W) caches are fully associative and coherent. They act as prefetch and write-back buffers for L1 data. The L2 cache line is 128 bytes in size. Each L2 cache has one connection toward the L1 instruction cache running at full processor frequency. Each L2 cache also has two connections toward the L1 data cache, one for the writes and one for the loads, each running at full processor frequency. Read and write are 16 bytes wide.

The third level (L3) cache is 8-way set associative, 8 MB in size, with 128-byte lines. Both banks can be accessed by all processor cores. The L3 cache has three write queues and three read queues: one for each processor core and one for the 10 Gigabit network. Ethernet and direct memory access (DMA) share the L3 ports. Only one unit can use the port at a time.

2.5. Networks

The JUGENE system uses five different networks dedicated to various tasks and functionalities of the machine. Each network has a different structure and topology of connections between the nodes of the system.

2.5.1. Three-dimensional torus: point-to-point network

The torus network is used for general-purpose, point-to-point message passing and multicast operations to a selected subset of nodes. The topology is a three-dimensional torus constructed with point-to-point, serial links between routers embedded within the Blue Gene/P nodes. A three-dimensional torus topology is available to the user application only if the assigned partition of the machine is a multiple of a midplane. Therefore, each of the nodes is connected to six nearest-neighbours. The target hardware bandwidth for each torus link is 425 MB/s in each direction of the link for a total of 5.1 GB/s bidirectional bandwidth per node. The three-dimensional torus network has a hardware latency within 100ns - 800ns.

2.5.2. Global tree and collective network

The global collective network is a high-bandwidth, one-to-all network used for collective communication operations, such as broadcast and reductions, and to move process and application data from the I/O nodes to the compute nodes. Each compute and I/O node has three links to the global collective network at 850 MB/s per direction for a total of 5.1 GB/s bidirectional bandwidth per node. Latency on the global collective network is less than 2 μ s from the bottom to top of the collective, with an additional 2 μ s latency to broadcast to all.

2.5.3. Global interrupt network

The global interrupt network is a separate set of wires based on asynchronous logic, which forms another network that enables fast, low latency signalling of global interrupts and barriers. Round-trip latency to perform a global barrier over this network for a 72 K node partition is approximately 1.3 μ s.

2.5.4. Functional or storage-access network

The 10 Gb Ethernet network consists of all I/O nodes that are connected to a 10 Gb Ethernet switch. The compute nodes are not directly connected to this network. All traffic is passed from the compute node over the global collective network to the I/O node and then onto the 10 Gigabit Ethernet network. A more detailed description can be found in Section 2.6.

2.5.5. Control network

The control network is used for system boot, debug, and monitoring. It provides run-time non-invasive service support as well as non-invasive access to performance counters.

2.6. I/O subsystem

The I/O subsystem of JUGENE is a system of three hardware layers with connectivity layers between them shown schematically in Figure 3. Within the Blue Gene/P itself there are a number of I/O nodes. These constitute the interface of the I/O subsystem to JUGENE's computational resources. The I/O nodes act as shared file system clients. They do not contain any storage components themselves, nor do they connect to dedicated storage components that could be considered local to any particular I/O node. For all file systems to which users have read and write access, the IBM General Parallel File System (GPFS) technology is used. A cluster of file servers presents Network Storage Devices (NSD) to their clients, performs meta-data operations and is responsible for the integrity of the shared files system. NSDs are the distributed shareable storage units from which GPFS file systems are built. They use logical units (LUN) that are served by a storage back-end of storage controllers and disk enclosures. The storage controllers use hardware RAID technology to pack several physical disks into an aggregate LUN with enhanced performance as well as better protection against failure than each of the individual physical disks involved can provide on their own.

Figure 3. The three layers of the I/O subsystem schematically

The fibre channel connectivity layer consists entirely out of cabling. It contains no switching hardware while the file server network connectivity layer is implemented with switching technology.

2.6.1. I/O nodes

The I/O nodes of the Blue Gene/P are nodes dedicated to I/O and do not permit the user to run any tasks of the user's parallel application. Each I/O node is connected via a 10 Gigabit Ethernet adapter to a network over which it accesses the GPFS shared file systems. This network, named in Figure 3 as the file serving network connectivity layer, is the functional network. The compute nodes, which run the application processes, do not have a connection to the functional network. Nevertheless, a user process can simply use I/O related system calls like `chdir()`, `open()`, `read()`, `write()`, or even `socket()`.

"Under the hood" the CNK forwards all file system and socket related operations to an I/O node using the Global tree network. This service is provided automatically and transparently by the CNK.

On the I/O node the forwarded operations are handled by the control and I/O daemon (CIOD), which subsequently hands them to the appropriate component of the GPFS client software. The typical path travelled by data which is handed to and returned by I/O functions on a compute node, is presented schematically in Figure 4.

Figure 4. I/O forwarding, function shipment, in more detail. The bi-directional red arrows show the typical path travelled by data associated with the function calls issued by an application process running on a compute node.

The assignment of a set of compute nodes to their dedicated I/O node in the tree topology is static. It is determined by the number of I/O nodes plugged into a node board and the position of node boards with I/O nodes in a midplane. The set of compute nodes that share the same I/O node is usually called a *processor set* or *pset*.

Figure 5 shows a pset from the perspective of an I/O node on top.

Figure 5. I/O node with some of the topologically nearest compute nodes in its pset

The 10 Gb/s bandwidth of the I/O node's Ethernet interface together with the characteristics of the I/O nodes themselves is rate limiting for the I/O.

Important

Asynchronous I/O is not supported on Blue Gene/P. For example if asynchronous MPI I/O routines are used (`MPI_Iwrite . . .`) the code will run as if the corresponding blocking routines were used.

JUGENE's 600 I/O nodes are distributed across the system in the following way:

- 71 racks have 4 I/O nodes per midplane (one I/O node for 128 compute nodes, that means a pset contains 128 compute nodes)
- 1 rack (R87) has 16 I/O nodes per midplane (one I/O node for 32 compute nodes, that means a pset contains 32 compute nodes).

The following table summarizes the maximum and average I/O performance for a rack with 4 I/O nodes per midplane.

Table 1. Theoretical maximum and average available bandwidths at various levels of aggregation of computational resources

System Unit	Max. bandwidth	Avg. bandwidth
midplane	3.00 GB/s	2.00 - 3.00 GB/s
pset	0.75 GB/s	0.5 - 0.75 GB/s
compute node	850 MB/s	10 MB/s
single core	850 MB/s	2.5 MB/s

2.6.2. Shared file system (GPFS/NSD) servers

The GPFS clients on JUGENE's I/O nodes are served by a cluster of 28 IBM p6-570 servers, equipped with 8 cores. However, 4 servers are exclusively dedicated to storing GPFS meta-data of all file systems. The remaining 24 serve as data NSDs belonging to one of the three file system (classes):

WORK
HOME
ARCH

All servers are equipped with identical resources to access storage capacity on one side, and to communicate with their GPFS clients on the other side:

- 8 x 4 Gb/s Fibre Channel (FC4) host adapter ports
- 4 x 10 Gb/s Ethernet links into the functional network of the Blue Gene/P

The maximum aggregate bandwidth of the cluster of 24 data servers on the Blue Gene/P functional network is 120 GB/s. The maximum aggregate bandwidth of the server cluster on the side of the fibre channel adapters that connect to the storage boxes is 96 GB/s.

2.6.3. Dealing with contention on the functional network

The functional network of JUGENE consists of four fabrics, each with a Force10 E1200i switch with 224 10 Gb/s Ethernet ports. Even in these switches the overall bandwidth on all ports still exceeds the capacity that the backplane and forwarding engine can handle. Groups of four adjacent switch ports share a common path onto the backplane and into the forwarding engine. Members of the same 4-port group are competing for the same bandwidth whenever two or more of them are concurrently handling traffic. So, theoretically there is a fourfold oversubscription on each of the four fabrics.

The following port allocation strategy was developed and applied to reduce the probability that interfaces will actually be contending for the same bandwidth:

- Every GPFS/NSD server is directly linked to each of the four fabrics by plugging one of its interfaces into the first port of a 4-port group. This guarantees that no two GPFS/NSD server interfaces within the same fabric are ever competing for the same bandwidth.
- The four I/O nodes of a midplane are each hooked up to a different fabric. Thus, even the smallest jobs have the aggregate bandwidth of all four fabrics at their disposal.
- I/O nodes of neighboring midplanes in the same fabric are distributed over different 4-port groups of the switch.

To better grasp how the fairly balanced scheme of port allocation nonetheless allows considerable differences in the I/O bandwidth at the level of the fabric switch between identically sized jobs on JUGENE, Figure 6 presents a logical model of the port allocation on such a switch. Each of the 224 ports is represented by a square, and the squares are grouped in 56 groups. 142 unmarked green squares represent the connections of the midplanes of the production environment. Spreading them evenly across the available groups results in 30 groups with 3 midplane connections and 26 groups with 2 midplane connections: $(30 \times 3) + (26 \times 2) = 142$. The light green squares, marked $a_1 a_4$ and $b_1 b_4$, represent the connections of the I/O nodes of the deviant rack (R87) described in Section 2.6.1. It shows that the bandwidth of these midplanes is also four times that of normal midplanes at the switch level. The yellow squares represent the GPFS server connections. The darker yellow ones, marked M1 - M4, represent the meta-data servers. The grey squares, marked with a question mark, are not necessarily empty. Some may also connect a front end node or some auxiliary systems not directly related to JUGENE at all. Some hypothetical jobs, A, B, and C, having a certain number of midplanes at their disposal, have been added to the picture. Other jobs would normally be running concurrently as well, using other midplanes, but are not shown.

Figure 6. Logical model of port allocation on a fabric switch with 56 4-port groups. Each of the 56 groups has a 10 Gb/s bandwidth channel that is shared among its 4 members. The port allocation to I/O nodes, servers, front end nodes etc. is static hard wired. The allocation of jobs to midplanes, and hence to the ports used by the I/O nodes of these midplanes, is dynamically determined by a batch scheduler.

Jobs A and C both utilize 16 midplanes. But at the switch level, the bandwidth of job A is much more likely to be "squeezed" than that of job C. The peak bandwidth that job A can achieve is about 80 GB/s since it has only 8 channels at its disposal. Job C has 16 channels, hence its peak bandwidth at the switch is twice that of job A. Job C and job B would no doubt sometimes be contending over the bandwidths of channels 33 - 38. But such contention would be incidental, since the jobs are not likely to be continuously engaged in I/O. The I/O of the tasks within a job is very likely to be orchestrated and more or less simultaneous. So the tasks of job A are likely to be contending among themselves for the bandwidths of channels 6 - 13 when they - simultaneously - engage I/O.

2.7. File systems

On JUGENE three file systems for user files are available: WORK, HOME, and ARCH. In the user environment three corresponding shell environment variables are set to directories (entry points in these file systems) where the user has read and write access:

- \$WORK denotes the absolute path to the user's scratch directory
- \$HOME denotes the absolute path to the user's home directory
- \$ARCH denotes the absolute path to the user's archive directory

Users are strongly recommended to address file system locations solely in terms of these variables. Please note that all file systems are shared GPFS file systems. Consequently, \$WORK, \$HOME, and \$ARCH are to be regarded as absolute pointers into a unified namespace that is shared by all nodes. So for example, \$WORK/my_file1 will denote exactly the same file system location to all processes of a user, irrespective of the node they happen to run on.

2.7.1. WORK

WORK is primarily intended as a "scratch space" for jobs. It is implemented as a single file system with a net total storage capacity of 2.4 PB. WORK is the best file system to use for large scale and demanding I/O. So in many cases it is also the recommended file system to store the end results of jobs. If a job's end results have to be kept for a longer time they will have to be saved to \$HOME or \$ARCH.

Important

- Files that are older than 90 days will automatically be *deleted*
- There is no backup service in place for this file system

Limits are enforced on a per group basis, both for the amount of data and for the number of files. In this context anything that occupies an I-node (a separate meta-data record in the file system) is counted as a "file": regular files, directories, and symbolic links. The per group data limit is 20 TB. The per-group inode limit is 4 million.

2.7.2. HOME

HOME is intended as a general repository of user resources: source codes, binaries, libraries, files with job input parameters, job outputs that are consulted on a regular basis, etc. Currently there are three file systems in this class: one with a total net storage capacity of 600 TB, and two file systems with a net storage capacity of 300 TB. Despite the difference in size, all three file systems are comparable in performance. They are configured for somewhat less demanding I/O requests and somewhat smaller file sizes than the WORK file system.

A daily incremental backup service is in place, creating backups of all new and recently modified files. The backup service will skip files that are open and in the process of being modified by other processes while the backup service is running. But a file that has resided unmodified for at least 24 hours on a home file system will have a backup copy. Limits are enforced on a per group basis both for data and number of I-nodes. The per group data limit is 6 TB. The per-group I-node limit is 2 million.

2.7.3. ARCH

ARCH is intended as an archive facility. Job output results that have to be kept for some time (at most for the life time of the user's project) may very well become too large to be kept on the HOME file system. Basically all files that are to be kept but will not be actively used for some time can be moved to the archive. Currently there are three archive file systems. They are identical in terms of capacity and performance. Automated migration policies are in place on all archive file systems. Files that have resided on an archive file system for a while will have been migrated to tape. A daily incremental backup service is in place. If a file is migrated to tape, an independent backup copy, residing on another tape, exists as well.

Limits are enforced on a per group basis for the number of I-nodes. The per-group I-node limit is 2 million. There is no automatic enforcement of a data limit on archive file systems. PRACE projects are expected to respect a data limit of 20 TB.

Important

Users with sets of many small files are urged to organize such files into sets that are put in a single container file and to subsequently put only the container file in the archive. This significantly reduces the number of I-nodes within the archive file systems and thus will have a very beneficial effect on the overall performance of many routines that handle meta-data. Furthermore, it takes about 2 minutes per file to retrieve data from tape. Thus, trying to retrieve several thousand files from the archive is simply impossible.

Optionally the container file can also be compressed. The size of the (compressed) container file should not exceed 1 TB because of considerations concerning the efficiency of the tape back-end. The `tar` command is the most appropriate tool to create such container files. It also has options to list files in a tar archive, extract files, etc. Please consult the online `tar(1)` manual page for further information.

2.7.4. Performance of file systems

The performance of GPFS file systems is summarized in Table 2.

Table 2. File system performance

File system	File system bandwidth	GPFS block size	# midplanes
WORK	34.0 GB/s	4 MB	16
HOME	8.5 GB/s	1 MB	4
ARCH	2.8 GB/s	2 MB	1

The aggregate maximum sustained performance for each file system is shown in column 2. Column 3 lists the GPFS block size. In the last column the minimum number of midplanes is shown which a job must use in order to mobilize the full potential of the file system with I/O requests from the client side.

RAID5 and RAID6 technology tend to have slightly better read than write performance. Writing is also much more sensitive to having a non-optimal file system block size. The figure in column 2 is probably too optimistic for write access to the ARCH file system. From a practical point of view file system bandwidth matters more when something is put into the archive. When retrieving something from the archive, many files tend to be on tape and have to be restored to disk first. This process will take about 3 hours per TB, rather due to limitations of the tape back end than to limitations of the archive file systems.

The GPFS block size of a file system is also included here because it is a very important factor in tuning the I/O of an application. To get the best performance out of the GPFS file system the I/O request size should be a multiple of this block size and address block-aligned sections of a file.

The numbers given are only rough estimates based on the following assumptions:

- To deliver its maximum bandwidth to the application, the storage back end must be addressed in a balanced way.
- To have a fair chance of doing that, the application must have at least the same nominal bandwidth, evenly distributed over the four fabrics of the network as the collective of server interfaces that serve the file system.
- For reasons explained in Section 2.6.3 there will be some effect of decreasing marginal returns when more than one midplane is used. To compensate for that in a very crude way the estimate is set at 1.25 x the nominal value of the server-side network bandwidth, when more than a single midplane is needed.

2.8. Further reading, information and references

JUGENE documentation on the web

- System configuration [http://www.fz-juelich.de/ias/jsc/EN/Expertise/Supercomputers/JUGENE/Configuration/Configuration_node.html]
- Available file systems [http://www.fz-juelich.de/ias/jsc/EN/Expertise/Supercomputers/JUST/JUST_filesystems.html]
- File system limits [http://www.fz-juelich.de/SharedDocs/FAQs/IAS/JSC/EN/JUST/FAQ_Data_limitiations.html]
- PRACE White Paper: The JUGENE I/O Subsystem, its Architecture, Guidelines and Tools for Using it Efficiently [http://www.prace-ri.eu/IMG/pdf/The_JUGENE_IO_Subsystem_its_Architecture_Guidelines_and_Tools_for_Using_it_Efficiently.pdf]

General related information

- IBM Redbook: IBM System Blue Gene Solution: Application Development [<http://www.redbooks.ibm.com/redbooks/SG247287/wwhelp/wwhimpl/java/html/wwhelp.htm>]

3. System Access

3.1. Application for an account

Members of an approved PRACE project apply online [https://dispatch.fz-juelich.de:8812/nic_account_ident/back=/RESOURCES&xxlang=english] for their accounts on JUGENE.

For authentication an email-callback procedure starts. Afterwards, the applicant is asked for the ID assigned to the project from FZJ (this has been made known to the project-leader from FZJ-Dispatch by mail; the ID usually starts with the prefix pr). After filling in the project-ID, the applicant is asked for his or her personal data and any further information needed. During this procedure an ssh-key has to be uploaded, detailed information about creating such a key can be found in Section 3.3. Finally, the application has to be submitted electronically. Also the printed version has to be sent to FZJ-Dispatch after it has been signed by the applicant and the project leader. The applicant will be informed by mail as soon as the account has been created on the system.

3.2. How to contact FZJ-Dispatch

For questions applicants can contact FZJ-Dispatch. The application for an account must be sent by FAX or by postal mail:

Forschungszentrum Jülich GmbH
Jülich Supercomputing Centre, Dispatch
52425Jülich
Germany
phone: +49 2461 61 5642
fax: +49 2461 61 2810
<dispatch.jsc at fz-juelich.de>

3.3. Access to JUGENE

Users can login to JUGENE on the so called front-end or login nodes only. Interactive access to the I/O or compute nodes is not possible. JUGENE has two different login nodes named jugene3 and jugene4 which may be addressed with

```
jugene.fz-juelich.de
```

The front-end nodes have identical environments, but multiple sessions of one user may reside on different nodes which must be taken into account when killing processes. The access is only possible by using ssh connections with keys. The public ssh key can be generated on the system from which you want to access JUGENE.

3.3.1. Key generation

Linux/Unix

In order to generate a key pair open a shell and use the following command

```
ssh-keygen -b 2048 -t rsa
```

You are asked for a file name and location where the key should be saved. Simply take the default by hitting the enter key. This will generate the ssh key in the `.ssh` directory of your home directory (`$HOME/.ssh`). Next, you are asked for a passphrase. Please, choose a secure passphrase. It should be at least 8 characters long and should contain numbers, letters and special characters like `!@#$%^*() ..`

Important

You are *NOT* allowed to leave the passphrase empty!

Windows

You can generate the key pair using for example the PuTTYgen tool, which is provided by the PuTTY project. Start PuTTYgen and choose SSH-2 RSA at the bottom of the window and set the 'number

of bits in the generated key' to 2048 and press the 'Generate' button. PuTTYgen will prompt you to generate some randomness by moving the mouse over the blank area. Once this is done, a new public key will be displayed at the top of the window. Enter a secure passphrase. It should be at least 8 characters long and should contain numbers, letters and special characters like !@#\$%^* () . .

Important

You are *NOT* allowed to leave the passphrase empty!
Save the public and the private key. We recommend to use 'id_rsa.pub' for the public and 'id_rsa' for the private part.

3.3.2. Upload of the public key

The contents of the files id_rsa.pub key must be uploaded through the JCS online WEB interface when applying for an account. The public key can be uploaded also later [https://dispatch.fz-juelich.de:8812/upload_key_ident/back=/RESOURCES&xxlang=english] if necessary.

The key will be saved on your JUGENE account at

```
$HOME/.ssh/authorized_keys
```

Important

- If the file `$HOME/.ssh/authorized_keys` already exists it will be overwritten.
- Make sure there is no write access for group or world on the `$HOME` directory, otherwise ssh does not work.

3.3.3. Login to JUGENE

After you have generated and uploaded the key you can access JUGENE in the following way (Linux/UNIX):

```
ssh <userid>@jugene.fz-juelich.de
```

On Windows please use your ssh client, choose the authentication method 'public-key', import the key pair and login with your account at `jugene.fz-juelich.de`.

Tip

- *X11 forwarding (Linux/UNIX)*

If a login is done via multiple machines, the X11 forwarding must be enabled in the file

```
$HOME/.ssh/config
```

Add the following lines to this file on your local system:

```
PubkeyAuthentication yes
ForwardAgent yes
ForwardX11 yes
```

or use the `-X` flag when using ssh

```
ssh -X ...
```

- *Login shell*

The Login Shell on JUGENE is the Bourne-again shell (bash). Users are not allowed to change the login shell but they can switch to a personal shell within the login process. User's will find a template within the initial FZJ `$HOME/.profile`. You can choose your shell by setting the environment variable `USERSHELL` accordingly, for example setting

```
USERSHELL=/usr/bin/csh
```

will enable the C shell. Please see `$HOME/.profile` for details.

3.4. Further reading, information and references

JUGENE documentation on the web

- Generation of ssh key pairs [http://www.fz-juelich.de/ias/jsc/EN/Expertise/Supercomputers/JUGENE/FAQ/_node.html#faq1053514]
- Login to JUGENE [<http://www.fz-juelich.de/ias/jsc/EN/Expertise/Supercomputers/JUGENE/UserInfo/Logon.html>]

4. Production Environment

4.1. Accounting

Job accounting is done via a central database at FZJ and the information about all jobs are gathered once a day around midnight, based on information obtained from the LoadLeveler batch system. The FZJ billing procedure calculates the various resources that each user in the project actually uses in so-called contingent units (KE). The calculation formula is specified below.

4.1.1. Monthly quota

Every approved PRACE project has been granted a quota of CPU hours for usage on the system by the PRACE panel. In order to ensure that the system is used equally over time, quotas are divided evenly across the months of usage. The amount of CPU time available for the current month (CQ) is calculated from this monthly quota (MQ) and any time left over from the previous month (PQ):

$$CQ = PQ + MQ$$

Remaining quota from earlier months is no longer available, so "saving of cpu time" is not possible. At the end of an allocation period, any remaining quota is forfeited. Daily, for each job the quota used is debited to CQ. This account may be overdrawn to the amount of the monthly quota of the following month (up to -MQ) without affecting the processing priority of the job. Only when the MQ of the following month has also been used up all subsequent jobs will be assigned lowest priority for the rest of that month. Using MQ of the following month is possible, but only if the user's allowance for computing resources includes the following month. An overdrawn account in the preceding months is carried over into the CQ as a negative quota.

4.1.2. Billing formula

Jobs will be charged for wall clock time, that means for the time the physical nodes are occupied. Jobs will be charged regardless whether the nodes are processing the user's application or idling. This leads to the following billing formula:

$$KE = f_c * NN * TIME$$

NN is the total number of nodes in the requested partitions used by the job and TIME is the wall clock time duration for which the job occupied the nodes (in hours). The factor f_c is the price for the usage of one node, currently f_c is 0.039 (KE/h).

4.1.3. Overdrawn quota

Jobs run at a normal priority unless three monthly quotas (previous, current and next month's quota) are consumed. If the current quota account is overdrawn, then all subsequent batch jobs for all users from the same project will be put on hold until CPU capacity is free. The maximum time that can be requested to process jobs is reduced to 6 hours. Jobs that require more computing time will be rejected. The time used by the jobs will still be debited to the quota account as described above. Users will be informed by mail, when they run out of CPU quota.

4.1.4. Querying quota status

Here in this and the next section this guide describes the FZJ-procedures, which are also available for PRACE users. But PRACE users can also use the Distributed Accounting Report Tool (DART) developed in the DEISA and PRACE projects: DART [<http://winnetou.sara.nl/deisa/DART/>]

Users get information about their current quota status or the usage of jobs by using the command

```
q_cpuquota <options>
```

Useful options are given in Table 3.

Table 3. Selected options for the `q_cpuquota` command.

Option	Description
-?	usage information and all options
-j <jobstepid>	for a single job with specified id
-t <time>	for all jobs in the specified time period, for example: -t 01.05.2011-15.05.2011
-d <number>	for the last <number> days (positive integer)

4.1.5. Querying project status by the project leader

Project leaders are informed monthly by mail about the quota status of their project and the usage of each project member. Additionally they have the possibility to query the project status [https://dispatch.fz-juelich.de:8808/wwwadr_quota/back=/RESSOURCEN&xxlang=english] any time. The project ID has to be specified and for authorization an email-verification method is used.

4.2. Module environment

On JUGENE, compilers, tools, some general and scientific applications as well as libraries are provided to users through the module tool. For each application a specific module script is provided that defines all what is needed to let the corresponding application run. In other words, the user's environment is updated dynamically in a suitable manner. Among other configurations, module scripts include definitions of environment variables to make known the paths to executables, libraries, header files etc.

The module concept eases the use of software on JUGENE. There is no need for the user to figure out what is needed and where needed components are stored in the file system in order to use a certain piece of software. Furthermore, it allows providing different versions of a software package to the user; conflicts between different versions are avoided due to the possibility to load a certain configuration set while unloading another one.

On JUGENE there is a distinction between applications running on the front-end (login) nodes and back-end (compute) nodes. Applications, that are made available by modules on the compute nodes are stored under the directory `/bgsys/local/` whereas applications to be used on the front end are given in `/usr/local/`. Therefore, it is important to load the needed modules within the job script if the corresponding application (or library etc.) is needed for the runs on the compute nodes.

The module tool is used on the command line in the following way:

```
module <option>
```

In the following Table 4 the most important options of the module command are shown together with short explanations.

Table 4. Selected options for the module command.

Option	Description
<no option>	List of available options
avail	Lists all available modules
list	Lists all currently loaded modules
add load <module1> [<module2> ...]	Loads a module. It is allowed to load more than one module per command invocation.
rm unload <module1> [<module2> ...]	Removes loaded modules. It is allowed to remove more than one module per command invocation.
switch swap <module1> [<module2> ...]	Unloads module1 and loads module2
show <module>	Shows the actual changes that will take place in the environment when module is loaded
help <module>	Provides the user with some information about the module and the corresponding software package.

The command module avail shows that the modules are organized in categories in order to facilitate the identification of available software packages. The following categories - again distinguishing between front-end and back-end - are defined on JUGENE (Table 5).

Table 5. Module categories available for the front-end and the compute nodes on JUGENE.

front-end	back-end
/usr/local/modulefiles/TOOLS	/bgsys/local/modulefiles/TOOLS
/usr/local/modulefiles/SCIENTIFIC	/bgsys/local/modulefiles/SCIENTIFIC
/usr/local/modulefiles/MATH	/bgsys/local/modulefiles/MATH
/usr/local/modulefiles/COMPILER	/bgsys/local/modulefiles/COMPILER
/usr/local/modulefiles/IO	/bgsys/local/modulefiles/IO
/usr/local/modulefiles/MISC	/bgsys/local/modulefiles/MISC

Besides those modules that point directly to the corresponding applications, there is a further module named UNITE, which itself contains a whole bunch of modules that focus on analysing and debugging issues. The command module load UNITE makes them available to the user. These tools will be discussed in detail in Section 6 and Section 8.

4.3. Running and monitoring jobs

A user process executes on Blue Gene/P compute nodes in one of the three available modes: Symmetric multiprocessing (SMP) which is a default execution mode, Dual mode and Virtual Node mode (also called Quad mode).

4.3.1. SMP mode

Figure 7. Application allocation in SMP execution mode (source: Lawrence Livermore National Laboratory [<https://computing.llnl.gov/tutorials/bgp/>])

In symmetrical multiprocessing (SMP) mode each of the compute nodes executes a single process (MPI process). SMP mode is the default execute mode on the Blue Gene/P. In this mode processes may spawn threads on each of the available cores in the node resulting in four threads per one MPI process and per one compute node as depicted in Figure 7. In SMP mode all four cores on the node work symmetrically. This enables all processes and threads on one node to access the full memory of the node. Executing in SMP mode also gives the maximum amount of memory per process. OpenMP and Pthreads are supported in SMP mode and thus a mixed MPI/OpenMP parallelization model can be used.

4.3.2. DUAL mode

In DUAL mode (schematically shown in Figure 8), each compute node executes two processes (MPI processes) per node with a default maximum of two threads per process. In DUAL mode half of the available memory and cores in the node is assigned to the process. In this mode user may create two threads per MPI task. DUAL mode also supports the MPI/OpenMP programming model.

Figure 8. DUAL execution mode (source: Lawrence Livermore National Laboratory [<https://computing.llnl.gov/tutorials/bgp/>])

4.3.3. Virtual Node mode

The Virtual Node (VN) mode allows to execute four separate processes on one compute node (Figure 9). In this mode MPI applications can use all cores in a node (four MPI tasks per node). In Virtual Node mode threading is not available. Resources and network links of the node are shared by all processes. VN mode is intended to be used with applications parallelized with MPI without threads.

Figure 9. VN execution mode (source: Lawrence Livermore National Laboratory [https://computing.llnl.gov/tutorials/bgp/])

Tip

The choice of the execution mode is a user's decision and largely depends on the application implementation and requirements.

- Applications using a mixed MPI and OpenMP or Pthreads parallelization technique may benefit from SMP or Dual mode.
- Single-threaded applications that use only MPI for parallel execution *must* run in VN mode to use the system efficiently.
- I/O-intensive tasks that require a large amount of data to be transferred between nodes and CPU bound applications without high memory requirements benefit by using the Virtual Node mode.
- Applications that have the ability to use a large number of processors with a good scaling behavior may consider to be executed in VN mode.

4.3.4. Mode selection

The default execution mode is SMP. To specify execution in DUAL or VN mode users must pass the mode option to the application session through the `mpirun` argument for DUAL and Virtual Node mode respectively.

```
mpirun -mode VN
mpirun -mode Dual
```

For further information about the `mpirun` command see Section 4.3.5.4.

4.3.5. Running and monitoring batch jobs with LoadLeveler

Application execution on the JUGENE is managed by the LoadLeveler scheduling system. LoadLeveler allocates computing resources to run jobs of users. A user submits a job using a job command file. The LoadLeveler scheduler attempts to find resources within the machine to satisfy the requirements of the user's job. The scheduling of jobs depends on the availability of resources and the job priority on JUGENE is proportional to the nodes requested, this means jobs requesting larger core counts are privileged.

Once the job is submitted LoadLeveler controls its execution and monitors the state. Jobs submitted with LoadLeveler are running in a batch mode which means that users cannot interact with the application execution in general. Users may use the command line tools to check the job status.

4.3.5.1. Job classes and resource reservations

Jobs are submitted for execution to a job queue or a job class. A job class is a classification to which a job can belong regarding its attributes. On JUGENE classes are chosen automatically according to the number of nodes the user requests and the user cannot specify a class. For example, if the user wants to run on 512 nodes (1 midplane) the job will be automatically queued in the queue m001. The default wallclock time for jobs requesting 512 nodes or more is 6 hours, the maximum wallclock time is 24 hours. Jobs requesting less than 512 nodes can run at most 30 minutes.

There are two exceptions:

1. If users need to run jobs on the front-end nodes on JUGENE `job_type serial` needs to be chosen (see section Section 4.3.5.3).
2. For debugging purposes using less than one midplane a class `dbglong` exists which allows to run on smaller numbers of cores for at most 4 hours. This queue is only available upon special request.

A list of available classes as well as additional information about each class (such as the maximum wall time allowed, the maximum number of jobs which will be executed in parallel, etc.) can be obtained using the `llclass` command

```
llclass
```

The priority of a job is set according to the number of nodes requested; the larger the number of nodes requested the higher the priority of the job. The following table provides an overview over the available classes (ordered with descending priority).

Table 6. Available LoadLeverler classes on JUGENE ordered with descending priority. R87 denotes a dedicated rack with additional I/O nodes in order to support jobs requesting less than 512 nodes.

Class Name	Max. wall time	Default wall time	Max. jobs per user	Comment/Running on
m144	24:00:00	06:00:00	-	On demand only
m128	24:00:00	06:00:00	-	On demand only
m064	24:00:00	06:00:00	-	All
m032	24:00:00	06:00:00	-	All
m016	24:00:00	06:00:00	-	All
m008	24:00:00	06:00:00	-	All
m004	24:00:00	06:00:00	-	All
m002	24:00:00	06:00:00	-	All
m001	24:00:00	06:00:00	-	All
small	00:30:00	00:30:00	2	R87
dbglong	04:00:00	04:00:00	4	On demand only

4.3.5.2. Job submission and monitoring

Once the command file is created (see Section 4.3.5.3 to Section 4.3.5.6) the job is submitted using the `llsubmit` command:

```
llsubmit <Job Command File>
```

LoadLeverler submits the job to the queue and assigns a unique job id. The job is waiting in the queue until the requested resources are available. When resources are ready LoadLeverler initializes the nodes

and computing environment and starts the user application. To monitor the job status and print its attributes, a user may use the command

```
llq
```

To cancel the job execution the

```
llcancel <jobid>
```

command is used.

The following table summarizes the LoadLeveler command-line tools.

Table 7. Basic LoadLeveler commands for job control and monitoring.

Command	option	Description
llsubmit	<Job command file>	Submits a job to the queuing system
llq	<no option>	Lists queued jobs
	-l <Job ID>	Displays the attributes of the job
	-s <Job ID>	Displays the job status
	-u <user>	Displays all jobs of <user>
	-x -l <Job ID>	Displays more details about the job
llqx	<no option>	Shows detailed information about all jobs
llcancel	<Job ID>	Cancels (kills) a job
llclass	<no option>	Lists existing classes
llstatus	<no option>	Displays the LoadLeveler status

4.3.5.3. Job command file (job script)

A job file is a script that contains the job attributes, specifications of the requested resources and commands to run the application. This file should have two blocks of instructions:

1. a LoadLeveler job keywords block at the beginning of a file
2. one or more application script blocks

LoadLeveler keyword-statement lines begin with # and @ which can be separated by any number of blanks. The application block is a regular shell script which can contain any shell command. The LoadLeveler scheduler uses a number of generic keyword statements and some additional keywords dedicated to the Blue Gene/P system. Selected general LoadLeveler keywords are given in Table 8. Blue Gene/P specific LoadLeveler keywords are given in Table 9.

Table 8. Selected LoadLeveler job file keywords

Keyword	Value	Description	Default
#@job_name	<Job Name>	Name of the job	-
#@ll_res_id	<Reservation ID>	Reservation to be used for resource allocation	-

Keyword	Value	Description	Default
#@notification	start	Notification when job has started	never
	complete	Notification when job has ended	
	error	Notification when an error has occurred	
	always	=start +complete +error	
	never	No notification is sent	
#@notify_user	<Mail address>	Address to use for notifications	\$USER@localhost
#@wall_clock_limit	<hh:mm:ss>	Time limit for the job duration	Depends on job size
#@queue	<queue name>	Places the job in the corresponding queue	-
#@input #@output #@error	<file name>	Name of the files to use as standard input / output / error	/dev/null
#@environment	<ENVVAR> COPY_ALL	Specifies initial environment variables set by LL when your job step starts. If COPY_ALL is given all environment variables are passed to the job.	-

Table 9. Selected Blue Gene/P specific LoadLeveler job file keywords

Keyword	Value	Description	Default
#@job_type	serial bluegene	Specifies the type of job step to process. If serial is specified, the job will run on the front-end node, otherwise it will be executed on the compute nodes.	serial
#@bg_size	<int>	Size of the Blue Gene job in terms of number of compute nodes. The keywords bg_size and bg_shape are mutually exclusive.	32
#@bg_shape	<int> x <int> x <int>	Specifies the requested shape of a Blue Gene job in terms of number of midplanes in x,y, and z direction, respectively. The maximum shape on	No default

Keyword	Value	Description	Default
		JUGENE in 9x4x4. The keywords <code>bg_size</code> and <code>bg_shape</code> are mutually exclusive.	
<code>#@bg_rotate</code>	TRUE FALSE	Specifies whether the scheduler should consider all possible rotations of the given shape of the job when searching for a partition for the job.	TRUE
<code>#@bg_connection</code>	MESH PREFER_TORUS TORUS	Type of wiring requested for the partition.	MESH

Sample job scripts can be found on the system in the directory

```
/bgsys/local/samples/LoadL
```

Since LoadLeveler automatically selects the appropriate partition to run the job on, the option `#@bg_partition` cannot be used on JUGENE.

On JUGENE applications need always to be executed with the `mpirun` command in order to run on the compute nodes. Thus, the job command file must contain appropriate arguments and a correct call to `mpirun` that will execute the user application. Please see Section 4.3.5.4 for further information.

4.3.5.4. The `mpirun` command

Programs can be launched and controlled on JUGENE using the `mpirun` command. The general syntax of this command is

```
mpirun <options>
```

`mpirun` offers the possibility to control the environment and the execution of an application using numerous parameters which can either be set by command-line options or by environment variables. The command-line options have higher priority, this means they override parameters specified by environment variables. In the following we describe some useful parameters for `mpirun` giving the command-line option and the corresponding environment variable.

Table 10. Command-line options and environment variables for the `mpirun` command.

Command-line option	Environment variable	Description
<code>-args "prg_args"</code>	<code>MPIRUN_ARGS = "prg_args"</code>	Passes <code>prg_args</code> to the launched application on the compute node.
<code>-env "ENVVAR=value"</code>	<code>MPIRUN_ENV = "ENVVAR=value"</code>	Sets the environment variable <code>ENVVAR</code> to <code>value</code> in the environment of the job on the compute nodes.
<code>-env_all</code>	<code>MPIRUN_EXP_ENV_ALL</code>	Exports all environment variables in the current environment of <code>mpirun</code> to the job on the compute nodes.
<code>-exe executable</code>	<code>MPIRUN_EXE="executable"</code>	Specifies the full path to the executable to be launched on

Command-line option	Environment variable	Description
		the compute nodes. The path must be specified as seen by the I/O and the compute nodes.
<code>-exp_env ENVVAR</code>	<code>MPIRUN_EXP_ENVVAR = "ENVVAR"</code>	Exports the environment variable <code>ENVVAR</code> in the current environment of <code>mpirun</code> to the job on the compute nodes. More than one variable can be exported with a comma-separated list.
<code>-mapfile mapfile</code>	<code>MPIRUN_MAPFILE = "mapfile"</code>	Specifies the order in which the MPI tasks are distributed across the nodes and cores of the partition reserved (see Section 7.2.4 for details).
<code>-mode SMP DUAL VN</code>	<code>MPIRUN_MODE = "SMP DUAL VN"</code>	Specifies the mode in which the job will run.
<code>-np n</code>	<code>MPIRUN_NP="n"</code>	Creates <code>n</code> MPI tasks (only needed if not the full reserved partition will be used).
<code>-verbose 1 2 3 4</code>	<code>MPIRUN_VERBOSE = "1 2 3 4"</code>	Sets the verbosity level of <code>mpirun</code> . Information generated by <code>mpirun</code> are passed to <code>STDERR</code> .

Tip

- In general it is not necessary to use the `-np` option of the `mpirun` command, because the number of MPI tasks is automatically computed according to the size of the partition requested and the execution mode (VN, DUAL, SMP) selected. For example, requesting 1024 nodes in DUAL mode will automatically create 2048 MPI tasks (2 tasks per node) without specifying the `-np` option. In fact, it is recommended to omit this option unless you want to use fewer tasks.
- It is recommended to use the `-verbose 2` option even if your job finishes with exit code 0. Events might occur during the run of your application which are not critical (that means the application does not crash) but which can provide hints how to set certain parameters in order to obtain a better performance. Such events are reported only at verbosity level 2 or higher.

4.3.5.5. Job command file example for pure MPI codes

The following example specifies a simple MPI job using a bash shell script. Lines beginning with `#<keyword>` are LoadLeveler keywords.

Example 1. Job command file for pure MPI codes

```
#!/bin/bash
#@job_name           = example_1
#@comment           = "BGP Job by Size"
#@error             = $(job_name).$(jobid).err
#@output            = $(job_name).$(jobid).out
#@environment       = COPY_ALL
#@wall_clock_limit  = 12:00:00
```

```

#@notification      = error
#@notify_user      = my_address@my.institution
#@job_type         = bluegene
#@bg_size          = 2048
#@bg_connection    = TORUS
#@queue

```

```
mpirun -mode VN -mapfile TXYZ -verbose 2 -exe application.x
```

mpirun will launch the executable `application.x` in Virtual Node mode. All environment variables are exported to the job environment. The topology of the requested partition is set to TORUS and the mapping order is set to TXYZ, that means the MPI tasks are distributed in such a way that each node is filled with 4 MPI tasks (T dimension first) before the next node is filled. 8192 MPI tasks are created in total. The user is notified by email if an error during the execution occurs.

4.3.5.6. Job command file example for hybrid MPI/OpenMP codes

The following example shows how to launch a hybrid application on JUGENE.

Example 2. Job command file for hybrid MPI/OpenMP codes

```

#@job_name          = example_2
#@error            = $(job_name).$(jobid).out
#@output           = $(job_name).$(jobid).out
#@environment      = COPY_ALL
#@wall_clock_limit = 12:00:00
#@notify_user      = my_address@my.institution
#@notification     = complete
#@job_type         = bluegene
#@bg_connection    = TORUS
#@bg_size          = 1024
#@queue

```

```

module load scalapack
mpirun -exe application.x -env OMP_NUM_THREADS=4

```

First, the module for the scalapack library is loaded. Then mpirun will launch the executable `application.x` in SMP mode (default mode, it is not necessary to specify `-mode SMP` here) and each task will start 4 threads. In total, 1024 MPI tasks are created. The user will be notified upon completion of the job.

4.3.6. Running interactive jobs with llrun

While developing applications it may be necessary to execute a job under interactive control. `llrun` creates and submits a LoadLeveler job under the direct control of the user's shell. `llrun` is invoked in the following way:

```
llrun [llrun_options] [mpirun_options] <executable>
```

`llrun` replaces `mpirun` and can be used with the same command line options like `mpirun`. There are only a few additional parameters. The following Table 11 lists the `llrun` options.

Table 11. Options for the llrun command

Option	Description
-B	submit batch job

Option	Description
-w hh:mm:ss	submit job with specified wallclock limit (Default: 00:30:00)
-o filename	do not run/submit job but save it to file filename
-q	do not queue interactive job if system has insufficient resources
-v	Verbose output
-h ?	Print help
-tv	Start the application with Totalview

4.3.7. The monitoring tool llview

llview is a client-server based application which allows monitoring of the utilization of the BG/P system and was developed at the Jülich Supercomputing Centre. It gives a quick and compact summary of different information like the usage of nodes/processors and the required resources of running and waiting jobs. In order to use llview the display needs to be exported correctly (login with `ssh -X`). Then the tool is invoked by

`llview&`

A typical display of llview is shown in Section 4.3.7. Graphical elements of llview are a node display, a usage bar, which gives a direct view of the job granularity, a list of running jobs and a list of waiting jobs, and a graph chart displaying the number of jobs in the different queues. For JUGENE two different views exist. The physical view shows which racks/midplanes the jobs are running on physically. The logical view shows how the partitions the jobs are running on are residing within the TORUS network. That means, midplanes which are logically adjacent in the TORUS network are depicted accordingly.

Figure 10. llview client displaying the status of JUGENE (physical view).

4.4. Further reading, information and references

JUGENE documentation on the web

- Accounting and quota [http://www.fz-juelich.de/ias/jsc/EN/Expertise/Supercomputers/JUGENE/UserInfo/CPU_Quota_Job_Accounting.html]
- Job classes and scheduling policy [<http://www2.fz-juelich.de/jsc/jugene/usage/reservation>]
- LoadLeveler on JUGENE [<http://www.fz-juelich.de/ias/jsc/EN/Expertise/Supercomputers/JUGENE/UserInfo/LoadLeveler.html>]
- The `llrun` command [<http://www2.fz-juelich.de/jsc/jugene/usage/load/llrun>]
- More job command file/job script examples [<http://www2.fz-juelich.de/jsc/jugene/usage/load/jobfile>]
- The `mpirun` command [<http://www.fz-juelich.de/ias/jsc/EN/Expertise/Supercomputers/JUGENE/UserInfo/mpirun.html>]
- The `llview` tool [<http://www2.fz-juelich.de/jsc/llview/>]

General related information

- IBM Redbook: IBM System Blue Gene Solution: Application Development [<http://www2.fz-juelich.de/jsc/jugene/usage/mpirun>]

5. Programming Environment/Basic Porting

5.1. Compilers

The Blue Gene/P programming environment consists of the two sets of compilers: The GNU Compiler collection for the Blue Gene architecture and the IBM XL compiler suite. The system supports cross-compilation and the compilers run on the front-end nodes. The compilers for the Blue Gene/P system have specific optimizations for the BG/P architecture. In particular, the XL family of compilers generates code appropriate for the double floating-point unit (FPU) of the Blue Gene/P system ("double hummer"). They also incorporate code optimizations specific to the Blue Gene/P instruction scheduling and memory hierarchy characteristics. The Blue Gene/P system has compilers for the C, C++, and Fortran programming languages. There is also support for the execution of Python-based user applications.

5.1.1. Available compilers

Since the JUGENE front-end nodes differ from the back-end nodes different compilers are necessary to generate executables for both types of nodes.

For the back-end nodes the IBM XL C/C++ and XL Fortran family of compilers should be the first choice for the compilation because of their specific optimization possibilities targeted for the Blue Gene/P architecture. XL compilers have a full support for the OpenMP version 2.5 standard and Fortran 2003 language standard. Each of the compilers from the XL family and the corresponding MPI wrappers have a thread-safe version that should be used for any multi-threaded application. The thread-safe version is invoked by appending "_r" to the corresponding compiler name, for example `bgx1f_r` or `mpix1c_r`. For Fortran XL compiler version 11.1, for C and C++ XL compiler version 9.0 are available.

The available XL compilers and compiler wrappers are summarized in Table 12.

Table 12. XL family of compilers - compiler invocation for the back-end compute nodes

Language	Compiler invocation	Compiler invocation - MPI wrapper
C	bgxlc, bgc89, bgc99, bgcc	mpixlc, mpixlc_r
C++	bgxlc++, bgxlc	mpixlcxx, mpixlcxx_r
Fortran	bgxlf, bgxlf90, bgxlf95, bgxlf2003, bgf77, bgf90, bgf95, bgf2003	mpixlf77, mpixlf90, mpixlf95, mpixlf2003, mpixlf77_r, mpixlf90_r, mpixlf95_r, mpixlf2003_r

A collection of GNU compilers for C, C++ and Fortran is also available on JUGENE (version 4.1.2 and 4.3.2). These compilers do not support some features of the Blue Gene/P architecture. In particular, GNU compilers do not generate highly optimized code for the Blue Gene/P platform and do not automatically generate code for the double FPU. GNU compilers are thread-safe but do not support OpenMP in the default version (4.1.2) of the compiler collection of the Blue Gene/P system. In order to use OpenMP with the GNU compilers you must use version 4.3.2 (see Section 5.4).

Table 13. GNU compiler collection for Blue Gene/P - compiler invocation for the back-end compute nodes.

Language	Compiler invocation	Compiler invocation - MPI wrapper
C	powerpc-bgp-linux-cc	mpicc
C++	powerpc-bgp-linux-g++	mpicxx
Fortran	powerpc-bgp-linux-gfortran	mpif77, mpif90

Additionally the corresponding compilers for the front-end nodes are available (XL and GNU compilers). Table 14 gives an overview over the invocation of the XL and gcc compilers for the front-end nodes.

Table 14. Compiler invocation for the front-end nodes of JUGENE. The commands for the XL and GNU family of compilers are shown.

Language	XL compiler family	GNU compiler family
C	xlc	gcc
C++	xlc++, xlc	g++
Fortran	xlf, xlf90, xlf95, xlf2003	gfortran

5.1.2. Compiler flags

5.1.2.1. XL Compiler family

Default for compilation is `-qarch=450d`, which means the "double hummer" (450d) is used for the calculation if nothing else is specified.

This may be suboptimal. Experiences with various applications have shown that the double hummer needs some preconditions to work optimal (see Section 7.1.1.3 for further information). Therefore, the use of 450d does not always lead to an optimum but sometimes even can extend the calculation time.

It is therefore recommended to test all applications with both options, `-qarch=450` and `-qarch=450d` and compare the results and the calculation times. The option `-qtune` should always be specified as `-qtune=450`.

We recommend to start with `-O2 -qarch=450 -qtune=450` and increase the level of optimization stepwise according to Table 15. Always check that the numerical results are still correct when using more aggressive optimization flags. For OpenMP codes, please add `-qsmp=omp -qthreaded`.

Table 15. Compiler flags for XL compilers in the order of increasing optimization potential.

Optimization level	Description
<code>-O2 -qarch=450 -qtune=450</code>	Basic optimization
<code>-O3 -qstrict -qarch=450 -qtune=450</code>	More aggressive optimizations are performed, no impact on accuracy
<code>-O3 -qhot -qarch=450 -qtune=450</code>	Aggressive optimization that may impact the accuracy (high order transformations of loops)
<code>-O4 -qarch=450 -qtune=450</code>	Interprocedural optimization at compile time, SIMD instructions
<code>-O5 -qarch=450 -qtune=450</code>	Interprocedural optimization at link time, whole-program analysis, SIMD instructions

Once you have determined the optimal flags you can switch to `-qarch=450d` which activates the double hummer and see whether this improves the performance further. If this option has no effect or even slows down the performance of your code, please check Section 7.1.1.3 for further information. If you benefit from using `-qarch=450d` option you can try further optimization with `-qhot=simd` option together with `-qarch=450d` option. This will force the compiler to generate SIMD instructions for double hummer FPU. Note that `-qhot=simd` is only supported with `-qarch=450d` switched on.

Important

The double FPU does not support exceptions, thus options related to exception handling are not valid with the `-qarch=450d` option.

The following XL Compilers compiler options are not supported on JUGENE:

- `-q64` (The Blue Gene/P processor is a 32-bit architecture and cannot use 64-bit mode)
- `-qaltivec`, `-qenablevmx` (The Blue Gene/P processor does not support vector data types nor VMX instructions)
- `-qpdf`, `-qshowpdf` (Profile directed feedback (PDF) is not fully supported on Blue Gene/P)

Please see Section 7.1.1.1 for a more detailed discussion and additional compiler flags for optimizing and debugging applications on JUGENE.

Tip

File extension: The XLF compilers treat Fortran source files differently depending on their file extensions (suffix):

- Files with suffixes `.f`, `.f77`, `.f90`, `.f95`, `.f03` are treated as files containing pure Fortran code (no pre-processor directives included)

- Files with suffixes `.F`, `.F77`, `.F90`, `.F95`, `.F03` are assumed to contain pre-processor directives and are pre-processed before compilation. By default the pre-processed files are deleted. If you want to keep them specify the `-d` compiler flag.

5.1.2.2. GNU Compiler Collection

The GNU Compiler Collection does not offer any specific compiler options specific for Blue Gene/P. To tune the application with GNU compilers users may start with the default set of options and apply the reference compile options if there are any. To check what options are in effect by default use the following command:

```
mpicc -Q -v -c
```

5.2. Available libraries

Numerous mathematical, scientific and communication libraries are available on JUGENE. You can get an overview by using the following command:

```
module avail
```

Libraries for the applications running on the JUGENE compute nodes are listed under

```
/bgsys/local/modulefiles/MATH
```

The libraries for the JUGENE front-end node can be found under

```
/usr/local/modulefiles/MATH
```

Further information about how to link your application with the different libraries can be obtained with

```
module help <library_name>[/<library_version>]
```

and

```
module show <library_name>[/<library_version>]
```

Here `<library_name>` should be replaced by the name of the library (such as `fftw`) and `<library_version>` by the corresponding version number (for example, `3.2.2`). The latter one can be omitted. In this case information about the default version is given.

5.2.1. Engineering and Scientific Subroutine Library (ESSL)¹

The vendor optimized numerical library for JUGENE is the ESSL (Engineering and Scientific Subroutine Library) provided by IBM. ESSL is a collection of high performance mathematical subroutines providing a wide range of functions for many common scientific and engineering applications. The mathematical subroutines are divided into nine computational areas:

- Linear Algebra Subprograms
- Matrix Operations
- Linear Algebraic Equations
- Eigensystem Analysis
- Fourier Transforms, Convolutions, Correlations and Related Computations
- Sorting and Searching
- Interpolation
- Numerical Quadrature

¹ The text has been taken in parts from the IBM ESSL documentation [<http://www-03.ibm.com/systems/software/essl/>]

- Random Number Generation

The ESSL Blue Gene Serial Library and the ESSL Blue Gene SMP Library run in a 32-bit integer, 32-bit pointer environment. Both libraries are tuned for IBM Blue Gene/P. A subset of the subroutines in the ESSL Blue Gene Serial Library uses SIMD algorithms that utilize the PowerPC 450 dual FPUs. The ESSL Blue Gene SMP library provides thread-safe versions of the ESSL subroutines. A subset of these subroutines are also multithreaded versions. Those multithreaded versions support the shared memory parallel processing programming model. Some of these multi-threaded subroutines also use SIMD algorithms that utilize the PowerPC 450 dual FPUs. The ESSL subroutines can be called from application programs written in Fortran, C, and C++.

Compiling and linking a Fortran90 program with the sequential and multithreaded version of ESSL, respectively, on JUGENE looks as follows:

```
mpixlf90_r name.f -L/bgsys/local/lib -lesslbg
mpixlf90_r name.f -L/bgsys/local/lib -lesslsmpbg
```

where `name.f` is a Fortran program calling routines from ESSL.

Compiling and linking a C program with the sequential version of ESSL on JUGENE looks as follows:

```
mpixlc_r name.c -L/bgsys/local/lib -lesslbg \
-L/opt/ibmcmp/xlf/bg/11.1/lib -lx1 -lxlopt -lxlf90_r \
-lxlfmath \
-L/opt/ibmcmp/xlsmp/bg/1.7/lib -lxlomp_ser -lpthread
```

For using the multithreaded version you need to use the following command:

```
mpixlc_r name.c -L/bgsys/local/lib -lesslsmpbg \
-L/opt/ibmcmp/xlf/bg/11.1/lib -lx1 -lxlopt -lxlf90_r \
-lxlfmath \
-L/opt/ibmcmp/xlsmp/bg/1.7/lib -lxlomp_ser -lpthread
```

For further information on ESSL, please see the IBM ESSL documentation [<http://publib.boulder.ibm.com/infocenter/clresctr/vxrx/index.jsp?topic=/com.ibm.cluster.essl.doc/esslbooks.html>]

5.3. MPI

5.3.1. MPI implementation

The MPI implementation for JUGENE is based on the MPICH2 implementation of the Mathematics and Computer Science Division (MCS) at Argonne National Laboratory. It supports the MPI 2.1 standard (with some exceptions, see below).

5.3.1.1. Compiling MPI applications

In order to compile your MPI applications please use the corresponding MPI compiler wrapper (either for the GNU or the XL suite of compilers) described in Section 5.1.1. For example, compiling your C code with MPI support you can use (IBM XL compiler)

```
mpixlc -o application.x routine.c
```

For further information about compilers and compiler flags please see Section 5.1.1 and Section 7.1.1 of this guide.

5.3.1.2. Running MPI applications

MPI applications can be run on JUGENE interactively with `llrun` or as batch jobs. For details please see Section 4.3.6 and Section 4.3.5.

5.3.1.3. Exceptions to the MPI standard

Some features of the MPI 2.1 standard are not supported on JUGENE.

- *Asynchronous (non-blocking) I/O*: Asynchronous I/O is not supported by the Blue Gene/P hardware. The MPI routines for non-blocking I/O (`MPI_File_iread`, `MPI_File_iread`) can be used without causing errors. However, the blocking I/O will actually be performed.

5.3.1.4. MPI extensions for Blue Gene/P

IBM provides extensions to MPICH2 in order to ease the use of the BG/P hardware. These extensions start with MPIX instead of MPI. Currently, only a C/C++ interface and no Fortran interface is available. In order to use the extensions, please include `mpix.h`:

```
#include <mpix.h>
```

and compile your program with the usual mpi compiler wrapper (`mpixlc`, `mpixlcxx`, ...).

The following routines are available:

```
int MPIX_Cart_comm_create(MPI_Comm *cart_comm)
int MPIX_Pset_same_comm_create(MPI_Comm *pset_comm)
int MPIX_Pset_diff_comm_create(MPI_Comm *pset_comm)

unsigned MPIX_torus2rank(unsigned x,unsigned y,unsigned z,
                        unsigned t)
void MPIX_rank2torus(unsigned rank,unsigned *x,unsigned *y,
                    unsigned *z,unsigned *t)

unsigned MPIX_Comm_torus2rank(MPI_Comm comm,unsigned x,
                              unsigned y,unsigned z,unsigned t)
void MPIX_Comm_rank2torus(MPI_Comm comm,unsigned rank,
                          unsigned *x,unsigned *y,
                          unsigned *z,unsigned *t)

int MPIX_Get_properties(MPI_Comm comm, int *prop_array)
int MPIX_Get_property(MPI_Comm comm, int prop, int *result)
int MPIX_Set_property(MPI_Comm comm, int prop, int value)
```

MPIX_Cart_comm_create creates a four-dimensional Cartesian communicator that mimics the exact hardware on which it is run. It will only work properly if the application runs on *ALL* nodes of a partition. For example, if you reserve 512 nodes your application *must not* use less than 512 nodes. Because of MPICH2 dimension ordering, the associated arrays (like `coords`, `sizes`, and `periods`) are in `[t, z, y, x,]` order so that the rank in `cart_comm` matches the rank in `MPI_COMM_WORLD`.

MPIX_Pset_same_comm_create creates a communicator such that all nodes in the same communicator are served by the same I/O node.

MPIX_Pset_diff_comm_create creates a communicator such that all nodes in the same communicator are served by a different I/O node.

MPIX_torus2rank returns the mapped rank based on the physical X, Y, Z, and T coords.

MPIX_rank2torus returns the physical X, Y, Z, and T coords based on the mapped rank.

MPIX_Comm_torus2rank returns the communicator rank based on the physical X, Y, Z, and T coords.

MPIX_Comm_rank2torus returns the physical X, Y, Z, and T coords based on the communicator rank.

`MPIX_Get_properties` retrieves the values of all the properties of the specified communicator.

`MPIX_Get_property/MPIX_Set_property` gets/sets the corresponding property for the specified communicator.

5.4. OpenMP

OpenMP [<http://openmp.org>] (Open Multi-Processing) is a well known set of compiler directives and API (Application Programming Interface) allowing one to develop parallel codes in a shared memory environment. It defines directives for the C, C++ and Fortran programming languages. On Blue Gene/P, the full OpenMP 2.5 standard is supported by the IBM compilers, with the limitation that one has to use the *thread-safe* versions of the compilers. This means that as soon as you intent to compile a code with the OpenMP support enabled, you have use the compilers with names ending with a "_r". See Section 5.1.1 for more details.

Moreover, one should be aware that OpenMP is only supported for the back-end nodes by the GNU compilers for version 4.2 or higher. The default version for GNU compilers on JUGENE is 4.1.2. Therefore, one has to load the necessary module to compile OpenMP code with a GNU compiler:

```
module load gcc/4.3.2
```

5.4.1. Compiler flags

For the IBM compilers, the OpenMP support is enabled with `-qsmp=omp`.

In addition, the thread-safety of all the optimizations performed and libraries linked has to be ensured. This is done by using the thread-safe compilers: `bgxlf_r`, `bgxlf90_r`, `bgxlf95_r`, `bgxlf2003_r`, `bgxlc_r`, and `bgxlc++_r`, or `mpixlf77_r`, `mpixlf90_r`, `mpixlf95_r`, `mpixlf2003_r`, `mpixlc_r`, and `mpixlcxx_r` for the mpi wrappers, depending on the targeted language. Using those versions of compilers will by default add the `-qthreaded` option. Any attempt to use `-qsmp=omp` to compile OpenMP code without using the "_r" version of compiler should lead to plenty of errors at link time such as:

```
libxlsmp.a(parregion.32.o): In function `SpinWait':
parregion.c:(.text+0x340): undefined reference to `pthread_yield'
parregion.c:(.text+0x36c): undefined reference to `pthread_yield'
```

For the GNU compilers of version greater or equal to 4.3.2, the OpenMP support is enabled with `-fopenmp`.

Since those compilers generate by default thread-safe code, no specific version or extra switch needs to be added.

5.4.2. Using OpenMP in different execution modes

OpenMP is supported on the Blue Gene/P for the two modes that support shared memory. Those are the SMP mode described Section 4.3.1 and the DUAL mode described Section 4.3.2. Either of the two modes should be selected with the corresponding `-mode` option to the `mpirun` or `llrun` command, as described in Section 4.3.4. In addition, the `OMP_NUM_THREADS` environment variable should be set and passed to `mpirun` or `llrun` coherently with the chosen mode.

Tip

In general there is no need to adjust the number of tasks to run with `-np` as it is done automatically by the system to reflect the number of nodes and the mode chosen.

The command line for running an OpenMP code should then look like:

- *In SMP mode* : ²

```
mpirun -env "OMP_NUM_THREADS=4" -exe myOMPcode.x [...]
```

- In *DUAL* mode :

```
mpirun -mode DUAL -env "OMP_NUM_THREADS=2" -exe myOMPcode.x [...]
```

5.5. Further reading, information and references

JUGENE documentation on the web

- Compiling and Tuning Applications on JUGENE [http://www.fz-juelich.de/sid_B56DA772F9C4DD0F1CE4199456DB9A66/ias/jsc/EN/Expertise/Supercomputers/JUGENE/UserInfo/CompilingTuning.html]
- ESSL [http://www2.fz-juelich.de/jsc/mathsoft/sd_libs/essl/]

General related information

- IBM Redbook: IBM System Blue Gene Solution: Application Development [<http://www.redbooks.ibm.com/redbooks/SG247287/wwhelp/wwhimpl/java/html/wwhelp.htm>]
- XL Compilers for Blue Gene [<http://publib.boulder.ibm.com/infocenter/compbgpl/v9v111/index.jsp?topic=/com.ibm.bg9111.doc/bgusing/related.htm>]
- Using the IBM XL Compilers for Blue Gene [http://bluegene.epfl.ch/vac_pdf/bg_using_xl_compilers.pdf]
- IBM ESSL documentation [<http://publib.boulder.ibm.com/infocenter/clresctr/vrxr/index.jsp?topic=/com.ibm.cluster.essl.doc/esslbooks.html>]
- OpenMP [<http://openmp.org>]

6. Performance Analysis

6.1. Available performance analysis tools

6.1.1. gprof

`gprof` - the GNU Profiler - is the basic tool to analyze program execution profiles. It is a good starting point for profiling your application. `gprof` produces an execution profile on the basis of the call graph profile file (`gmon.out` by default). The profile file is created by programs that are compiled and/or linked with the `-p` or `-pg` option. It works for C and Fortran programs and both GNU and XL compilers.

To produce an execution profile of your application you need to compile and link your application with the `-p` or `-pg` option. After the program execution is finished the profiling data is collected in `gmon.out.x` files, where `x` corresponds to the MPI rank of a process that produced the data. This is extended functionality of the GNU toolchain introduced on Blue Gene/P to support MPI based application with `gprof`. Note that support for threaded applications is not implemented in `gprof` on Blue Gene/P. In case of threaded programs running in SMP mode on computing nodes, most likely the master thread only will be profiled.

To start with the most basic timer-tick profiling information at the machine instruction level, use the `-p` option on the link command only. Without any additional options in the compile command there will be least overhead added to the program execution time. Furthermore, there will not be collected any call graph information.

In order to proceed with a procedure level profiling you need to include the `-p` option in the compile command for all application source code files. This will collect additionally call graph information. This will add an additional performance overhead. Note also that compilation with

aggressive optimization options may alter the structure of the reported call graph due to the possible compiler-based code reorganization.

To enable the full level of profiling you need to include the `-pg` option in all compile and link commands. In that case call-graph, statement-level, basic block, and machine- instruction profiling data is collected. This level of profiling will introduce the most overhead in an overall program performance.

To analyze the data collected in the `gmon.out.x` files during the program execution you need to start `gprof` on a front-end node to obtain a flat profile:

```
gprof -p program-binary profile-file-list
```

If you use the `-sum` option in the `gprof` command line, it would merge all `gmon.out.x` files into one `gmon.out` file.

In cases where a large number of `gmon.out.x` files is collected, for example, if a large number of compute nodes is used for execution, users may find it impossible to process all of these files due to the limit on input arguments in the Linux system. To overcome this limitation use the `-sum` option on the `gprof` command line. This will instruct `gprof` to search the current directory for all `gmon.out.x` files with `X` in a continuous sequence.

6.1.1.1. gprof examples

The following example shows the flat profile for a simple parallel program that operates on matrices. The profile shows that most of time the program spends in functions called `mat_cmp` and `mat_mul`. There is also a significant part of the runtime consumed by `sin` and `cos` calculations.

Example 3. Flat Profile

Flat profile:

Each sample counts as 0.01 seconds.

%	cumulative	self	calls	self	total	name
time	seconds	seconds		s/call	s/call	
30.60	4655.25	4655.25	48	96.98	96.98	mat_cmp
27.23	8798.60	4143.35	64	64.74	64.74	mat_mul
23.02	12301.23	3502.63				sin
19.10	15207.63	2906.40				cos
0.00	15213.24	0.36				mmap
0.00	15213.76	0.00	16	0.00	549.91	main

Each row in a profile corresponds to the function in the analyzed program. Functions are sorted by decreasing runtime spent. The meaning of the fields in a profile is as follows:

`time`

The percentage of the total execution time that program spent in this function.

`cumulative seconds`

Total number of seconds that program spent executing this functions, plus the time spent in all the functions above this one.

`self seconds`

The number of seconds accounted for this function only.

`calls`

The total number to the function calls.

```
self s/call
```

The average time in seconds spent in this function per call.

```
total s/call
```

The average time in seconds spent in this function and its descendants per call.

```
name
```

The name of the function.

If the s field in a table is left blank the corresponding function was never called or the information cannot be determined. In this example the sin and cos functions are not profiled because the versions from the math library were used which is not compiled with profiling enabled.

Example 4. Line Level Flat Profile

Flat profile:

Each sample counts as 0.01 seconds.

% time	cumulative seconds	self seconds	self calls	self Ts/call	total Ts/call	name
24.51	4018.92	4018.92				mat_mul (cannon_cmp.c:22 @ 1001524)
11.44	5894.25	1875.33				__sin (s_sin.c:334 @ 1138ed0)
8.67	7315.83	1421.58				mat_cmp (cannon_cmp.c:35 @ 10016d8)
7.93	8616.51	1300.68				mat_cmp (cannon_cmp.c:34 @ 10016b0)
7.13	9786.35	1169.84				__cos (s_sin.c:578 @ 1138078)
7.13	10955.63	1169.28				mat_cmp (cannon_cmp.c:33 @ 1001688)
6.47	12017.09	1061.46				mat_mul (cannon_cmp.c:21 @ 1001584)
4.89	12819.35	802.26				mat_cmp (cannon_cmp.c:32 @ 1001714)
4.13	13496.15	676.80				__sin (s_sin.c:89 @ 1138d64)
2.92	13975.28	479.13				__cos (s_sin.c:343 @ 1137dbc)
1.55	14228.67	253.39				__sin (s_sin.c:100 @ 1138d3c)
1.49	14472.77	244.10				__cos (s_sin.c:348 @ 1137d9c)
1.44	14709.26	236.49				__cos (s_sin.c:348 @ 1137d88)
1.44	14945.63	236.37				__sin (s_sin.c:89 @ 1138d38)
1.43	15179.81	234.18				__sin (s_sin.c:100 @ 1138d28)
1.43	15413.78	233.97				__cos (s_sin.c:343 @ 1137d98)
1.08	15591.18	177.40				__cos (s_sin.c:343 @ 1137db4)
0.90	15738.35	147.17				__sin (s_sin.c:89 @ 1138d44)
0.82	15872.69	134.34				__sin (s_sin.c:89 @ 1138d5c)
0.80	16004.63	131.94				__sin (s_sin.c:89 @ 1138d54)
0.76	16129.12	124.49				__cos (s_sin.c:578 @ 113806c)
0.76	16253.48	124.36				__cos (s_sin.c:343 @ 1137da4)
0.71	16370.64	117.16				__cos (s_sin.c:352 @ 1138070)
0.06	16380.59	9.95				__cos (s_sin.c:343 @ 1137d8c)
0.03	16385.94	5.35				__sin (s_sin.c:89 @ 1138d2c)
0.01	16387.07	1.13				mat_mul (cannon_cmp.c:20 @ 10015a0)
0.01	16387.98	0.91				mat_cmp (cannon_cmp.c:31 @ 1001730)
0.01	16388.81	0.83				mat_mul (cannon_cmp.c:21 @ 100150c)
0.00	16391.47	0.36				mmap
0.00	16396.00	0.00	64	0.00	0.00	mat_mul (cannon_cmp.c:15 @ 10014a0)
0.00	16396.00	0.00	48	0.00	0.00	mat_cmp (cannon_cmp.c:25 @ 1001600)
0.00	16396.00	0.00	16	0.00	0.00	main (cannon_cmp.c:39 @ 10017a0)

In order to analyze the run-time profile at source-code-line-level accuracy use the `-l` option with the `gprof` command. For the complete information on line-by-line profiling add the `-g` and `-qfullpath` options to the compile command of the target source files. The example above shows line-by-line profile output from `gprof`. The profile consist of the same information as the previous flat profile but with execution time samples splitted between actual lines in the source code (`cannon_cmp.c`). Note that generation of the line-by-line profile for complex programs can take significant time.

The call graph shows how much time was spent in each function and its children. The next example came from the same simple program as flat profile from the previous example.

Example 5. Call Graph

Call graph (explanation follows)

granularity: each sample hit covers 4 byte(s) for 0.00% of 15213.76 seconds

```

index % time      self  children   called      name
-----
[1]    57.8         0.00 8798.60   16/16      generic_start_main [2]
         0.00 8798.60   16         main [1]
         4655.25    0.00   48/48     mat_cmp [3]
         4143.35    0.00   64/64     mat_mul [4]
-----
[2]    57.8         0.00 8798.60           <spontaneous>
         0.00 8798.60   16/16     generic_start_main [2]
         0.00 8798.60           main [1]
-----
         4655.25    0.00   48/48     main [1]
[3]    30.6 4655.25    0.00    48         mat_cmp [3]
-----
         4143.35    0.00   64/64     main [1]
[4]    27.2 4143.35    0.00    64         mat_mul [4]
-----
[5]    23.0 3502.63    0.00           <spontaneous>
         sin [5]
-----
[6]    19.1 2906.40    0.00           <spontaneous>
         cos [6]
-----
[7]    0.0    0.36    0.00           <spontaneous>
         mmap [7]
-----

```

A detailed description of the call graph fields can be found in the `gprof` output. The `gprof` call graph shows entries separated by horizontal rows. Each entry in the call graph consists of several lines. The line with the index number at the left hand margin lists the current function. The lines above it list the functions that called this function, and the lines below it list the functions this one called.

Profiling data can be collected in an alternate format. To turn on the sequential storing of the observed executing instruction addresses at each interrupt instead of normal `gprof` counters, set `GMON_SAMPLE_DATA=yes` before the execution of the program. In that case data is collected in `gmon.sample.x` files. This allows the sequence of addresses to be reconstructed and it is a Blue Gene/P enhancement to the GNU `gprof` tool. Also these files tend to be much smaller than the `gmon.out.x` files. To process the `gmon.sample.x` files, use the `/bgsys/drivers/ppcfloor/gnu-linux/bin/powerpc-bgp-linux-gprof` command, which is a Blue

Gene/P specific version and will recognize the file format. It will produce the same output as in the previous examples. Use the `-d` option with the Blue Gene/P `gprof` command to display the program counter values in the order in which they were collected and the `-sum` option to aggregate data into a `gmon.sum` file that is in standard `gmon.out` format.

6.1.2. Performance Application Programming Interface (PAPI)

PAPI is a library and associated utilities for portable access to hardware/system performance counters. A core component for CPU/processor counters provides counts of instructions, floating-point operations, branches predicted/taken, cache accesses/misses, TLB misses, cycles, stall cycles, etc., though not all events are supported by BG/P hardware. Additional counters provide counts of events and bytes transferred with the BG/P torus network. Predefined events are derived from available native counters, for example, total numbers of floating-point operations (excluding loads and stores) are constructed with

```
PAPI_FP_OPS = PNE_BGP_PU0_FPU_ADD_SUB_1 + PNE_BGP_PU1_FPU_ADD_SUB_1
+ PNE_BGP_PU0_FPU_MULT_1 + PNE_BGP_PU1_FPU_MULT_1
+ 2*PNE_BGP_PU0_FPU_FMA_2 + 2*PNE_BGP_PU1_FPU_FMA_2
+ 13*PNE_BGP_PU0_FPU_DIV_1 + 13*PNE_BGP_PU1_FPU_DIV_1
+ PNE_BGP_PU0_FPU_OTHER_NON_STORAGE_OPS
+ PNE_BGP_PU1_FPU_OTHER_NON_STORAGE_OPS
+ 2*PNE_BGP_PU0_FPU_ADD_SUB_2 + 2*PNE_BGP_PU1_FPU_ADD_SUB_2
+ 2*PNE_BGP_PU0_FPU_MULT_2 + 2*PNE_BGP_PU1_FPU_MULT_2
+ 4*PNE_BGP_PU0_FPU_FMA_4 + 4*PNE_BGP_PU1_FPU_FMA_4
+ 2*PNE_BGP_PU0_FPU_DUAL_PIPE_OTHER_NON_STORAGE_OPS
+ 2*PNE_BGP_PU1_FPU_DUAL_PIPE_OTHER_NON_STORAGE_OPS
```

To be able to use PAPI load the following modules: `module load UNITE papi`

Available PAPI preset and BG/P native counters are documented in `$PAPI_ROOT/etc`.

On BG/P, PAPI is not usable in virtual node (VN) mode. PAPI also doesn't distinguish events counted by shared hardware counters, such as those for the BG/P network.

The PAPI API can be used to manually configure and assess counters, however, it is more commonly used by tools such as Scalasca (Section 6.1.3), TAU (Section 6.1.4) and Vampir (Section 6.1.5). Since hardware counters are shared resources, they can't simultaneously be used by performance measurement tools and the subject application itself.

6.1.2.1. Further information

Since a complete description of PAPI is far beyond the scope of this guide, please see the PAPI homepage [<http://icl.cs.utk.edu/>] for further information.

6.1.3. Scalasca

Scalasca is a software tool that supports the performance optimization of parallel programs by measuring and analyzing their runtime behavior. The analysis identifies potential performance bottlenecks - in particular those concerning communication and synchronization, and offers guidance in exploring their causes.

Analyzing your code with Scalasca involves the following steps

1. Instrumenting the application code
2. Analyzing the instrumented code by running it with measurement configured
3. Examine the analysis results
4. (Optional) Refine the measurement configuration and re-run

6.1.3.1. Instrumenting your code

First you need to load the corresponding modules.

```
module load UNITE scalasca
```

You can obtain a short introduction/help using

```
module help scalasca
```

or running the `scalasca` command on its own.

After you have loaded the Scalasca module you need to recompile your application to instrument it for using Scalasca. Simply prepend your compiler command with

```
scalasca -instrument
```

For example, if you are using the `mpixlf90_r` compiler wrapper to compile your application, use `scalasca -instrument mpixlf90_r` instead:

Example 6. Makefile modified for Scalasca instrumentation

```
...
PRE = scalasca -instrument
F90 = $(PRE) mpixlf90_r
...
%.o: %.f90
    $(F90) $(F90FLAGS) -c -o $@ $<
$(EXE): $(OBJ)
    $(F90) $(F90FLAGS) $(LDFLAGS) -o $@ $(OBJ)
...
```

6.1.3.2. Analyzing (running) the instrumented code

In order to analyze your code with Scalasca you run the instrumented executable of your application the same way as you do without Scalasca, just prepend `scalasca -analyze` to your usual `mpirun` command line. You may also need to quote certain `mpirun` options by enclosing them in quotation marks as shown in the following job command file example.

Example 7. Job command file for a Scalasca experiment

```
#@job_name           = scalasca_profile
#@comment            = "Scalasca profile analysis"
#@output             = scalasca_prof.out
#@error              = scalasca_prof.err
#@environment        = COPY_ALL
#@job_type           = bluegene
#@notification       = never
#@bg_size            = 32
#@wall_clock_limit   = 00:30:00
#@queue

module load UNITE scalasca
scalasca -analyze mpirun "-mode VN" application.x args
```

This job file will launch your application in VN mode on 32 nodes (128 MPI tasks) and perform a Scalasca profile analysis.

As a result you will obtain a directory named `./epik_application_128_sum` where the Scalasca results are stored. Furthermore, information are printed to `STDOUT` and `STDERR`. They could look similar to the following examples:

Example 8. `STDOUT` example of a Scalasca run

```
[00000]EPIK: Created new measurement archive ./epik_application_128_sum
[00000]EPIK: Activated ./epik_application_128_sum [NO TRACE] (0.024s)
...
      [STDOUT of application.x]
...
[00000]EPIK: Closing experiment ./epik_application_128_sum
[00000]EPIK: 224 unique paths (223 max paths, 6 max frames, 0 unknowns)
[00000]EPIK: Unifying... done (0.017s)
[00000]EPIK: Collating... done (0.088s)
[00000]EPIK: Closed experiment ./epik_application_128_sum (0.125s)
```

Example 9. `STDERR` example of a Scalasca run

```
S=C=A=N: Scalasca 1.3.3 runtime summarization
S=C=A=N: ./epik_application_128_sum experiment archive
S=C=A=N: Mon Sep 26 09:12:01 2011: Collect start
/usr/local/bin/mpirun -mode VN -E EPK_TITLE application_128_sum\
-E EPK_LDIR . -E EPK_SUMMARY 1 -E EPK_TRACE 0 application.x
S=C=A=N: Mon Sep 26 09:14:42 2011: Collect done (status=0) 161s
S=C=A=N: ./epik_application_128_sum complete.
```

6.1.3.3. Examine Scalasca analysis results

Example 7 will produce profile data of the run of the application `application.x` in a `epik_application_128_sum` directory.

To interactively explore the analysis results with Scalasca's CUBE GUI use the following command:

```
scalasca -examine -s epik_application_128_sum
```

Important

In order to be able to use the `cube3` GUI please make sure you are logged in with

```
ssh -X
```

If you are not directly connected to JUGENE, make sure you are using the `-X` option for all `ssh` connections and that your local system (laptop, PC) has a running X server!

For further information on how to use the GUI see

```
module help cube
```

and refer to the Scalasca documentation [<http://www.scalasca.org/download/documentation/documentation.html>]

The file `epik_application_128_sum/epik.conf` contains the values of all Scalasca environment variables that were in effect during the run of the experiment. When necessary adjusting one or more of these environment variables can be used to configure subsequent measurement runs, for example, adding one or more PAPI hardware counters (Section 6.1.2).

Furthermore, the file `epik_application_128_sum/epik.path` contains the call tree of your application execution.

To analyze the results further execute the following command:

```
scalasca -examine -s epik_application_128_sum
```

As a result you get an additional file `epik_application_128_sum/epik.score` which contains a table where all functions of your application are listed, the type of the function (such as an MPI function, a user function, etc.) and the time the application spent in this function (absolute and relative).

Finally, Scalasca provides you with an estimate about the amount of disk space necessary to perform a trace experiment, that means a time-stamped protocol of all events executed by your application:

```
...
Estimated aggregate size of event trace (total_tbc): 8111014272 bytes
Estimated size of largest process trace (max_tbc): 35620782 bytes
...
```

This means that when you run a trace experiment you will need about 8 GB of disk space (`total_tbc`). Furthermore, the largest trace size for a single process will be around 36 MB (`max_tbc`) which exceeds the default trace buffer size of 10 MB. To avoid disruptive flushing of trace buffers to disk during measurement, larger buffers can be configured by setting the environment variable `ELG_BUFFER_SIZE` to at least `max_tbc` and/or refining measurement by specifying a filter file to reduce measurement overhead.

A measurement filter can be used to exclude some functions or subroutines from the experiment, for example because they introduce too much overhead and are not particularly relevant for your analysis or belong to external libraries. In this case simply list the names of all functions (one per line) in an ASCII file `filter.txt`. The names of routines to be used in the the filter can be identified from the `epik.score` file. Add this filter to Scalasca analysis runs using the option `-f filter.txt`.

6.1.3.4. Refine the measurement configuration

To analyze the wasted waiting time associated with communication and synchronization inefficiencies such as late senders and load imbalances, a Scalasca trace experiment can be configured and the instrumented application rerun. To minimize measurement collection and storage overhead, remember to configure a measurement filter and/or adequate trace buffer sizes, best determined from the score report of a prior summary experiment as discussed in Section 6.1.3.3.

Here an example job command file to perform this trace experiment:

Example 10. Job command file for a Scalasca trace experiment

```

#@job_name          = scalasca_trace
#@comment           = "Scalasca trace analysis"
#@output            = scalasca_trace.out
#@error             = scalasca_trace.err
#@environment       = COPY_ALL
#@job_type          = bluegene
#@notification      = never
#@bg_size           = 32
#@wall_clock_limit = 00:30:00
#@queue

module load UNITE scalasca
export ELG_BUFFER_SIZE=36000000
scalasca -analyze -t -f filter.txt mpirun "-mode VN" application.x args

```

The `-t` option specifies that a trace will be collected and analyzed, stored in an experiment directory `epik_application_128_trace`.

The results of this experiment can be examined as described in Section 6.1.3.3.

6.1.3.5. Scalasca example

Scalasca has been used to analyse the execution performance of the three-dimensional reservoir simulator *PFLOTRAN* on JUGENE, using a test case comprising 850x1000x160 grid cells with 15 chemical species for 2E9 degrees of freedom, and although it scaled well to 65,536 processes various inefficiencies became increasingly significant. Developed by LANL/ORNL/PNNL, PFLOTRAN combines solvers for non-isothermal, multi-phase groundwater flow and reactive, multi-component contaminant transport. It consists of approximately 80,000 lines of Fortran90 and employs PETSc, LAPACK, BLAS and HDF5 I/O libraries, with MPI used both directly by the application and indirectly via these libraries.

The PFLOTRAN application and PETSc library were both instrumented using Scalasca, resulting in over 1,100 routines in an initial summary analysis report: those routines not found on execution callpaths to MPI operations were filtered during subsequent measurements, such that measurement dilation with respect to the uninstrumented application execution was reduced to an acceptable 5-15%. For executions of 10 simulation timesteps, each process required a trace buffer size (ELG_BUFFER_SIZE) of 32 MB, and total trace size grew to 2.0 TB with 65,536 processes, taking an additional 25 minutes for Scalasca trace collection and parallel analysis.

Figure 11 shows the Scalasca analysis report explorer GUI (CUBE) with a trace analysis of a 8192-processes SMP-mode execution on JUGENE. Load imbalance on 6-7% of processes along the top/front edge are clearly visible and due to the computational characteristics of that part of the problem geometry. A more significant imbalance that was found arises from the decomposition of grid cells onto processes. Both imbalances in (local) computation time combine to manifest as waiting time in associated MPI communication and synchronization quantified by Scalasca trace analysis (8% of total execution time as highlight in Figure 11). Even after addressing these imbalances, the large numbers of MPI_Allreduce operations performed each simulation timestep are the primary scalability inhibitor that grow to dominate execution time at large scales. MPI File I/O done with HDF5 also constitutes 8% of total execution time at this scale. Although this initialization cost can be amortized over longer simulation times, it was also identified as an important area to be reworked by the developers to improve large-scale performance.

Figure 11. Scalasca analysis report explorer GUI (CUBE) showing trace analysis of PFLOTRAN application execution on JUGENE with 8192 MPI processes.

6.1.3.6. Further information

Scalasca event traces can also be visualized with Vampir (Section 6.1.5), and Scalasca analysis reports (cubefiles) can also be examined with the TAU/ParaProf GUI (Section 6.1.4).

Since a complete description of the Scalasca tool is far beyond the scope of this guide, please see the Scalasca homepage [<http://www.scalasca.org/>] for further information.

6.1.4. Tau

The TAU performance system is a toolkit integrating a variety of instrumentation, measurement, analysis and visualization components, and with extensive bridges to and from other performance tools such as Scalasca and Vampir. ParaProf profile displays of a Scalasca analysis report (Section 6.1.3.5) are demonstrated in Figure 12. TAU is highly customizable with multiple profiling and tracing capabilities, targets all parallel programming/execution paradigms and is ported to a wide range of computer systems.

Figure 12 shows a color-coded routine execution time profile (upper right), a routine-wise performance breakdown for all processes (upper left), a distribution histogram of `MPI_Allreduce` time by processes (lower right) and a three-dimensional profile view. Note that by default ParaProf shows both routine and callpath profiles simultaneously, and one or the other typically needs to be disabled (as done in this example).

Before using TAU you need to load the corresponding modules.

```
module load UNITE tau
```

Figure 12. TAU/ParaProf GUI displays of Scalasca trace analysis report of PFLOTRAN application execution on JUGENE with 8192 MPI processes.

Important

In order to be able to use the TAU paraprof GUI please make sure you are logged in with `ssh -X`

If you are not directly connected to JUGENE, make sure you are using the `-X` option for all ssh connections and that your local system (laptop, PC) has a running X server!

6.1.4.1. Further information

Since a complete description of the TAU tool is far beyond the scope of this guide, please see the TAU homepage [<http://tau.uoregon.edu/>] for further information.

6.1.5. Vampir

Vampir is a tool for interactive event trace analysis, offering a visual presentation of dynamic execution behavior in an event timeline chart showing process/thread states and interactions, along with additional displays of communication statistics, summaries and much more. Browsing via zooming and scrolling updates linked displays and statistics to the visible time interval, and events can be selected for detailed examination as shown in Figure 13.

Figure 13. Vampir visualizations of full Scalasca trace and seventh timestep of PFLOTRAN application execution on JUGENE with 8192 MPI processes.

Vampir visualizes traces collected with VampirTrace or Scalasca (Section 6.1.3.5), and comes with an additional parallel server to handle larger traces. Figure 13 shows an initial view of the entire execution trace where a timeline for 50 of the 8192 MPI processes are visible, along with a matrix of MPI message transfer times organized by sender/receiver, and a routine execution time summary profile. MPI_Allreduce events and time are highlighted in red and seen to dominate the execution of pairs of processes. After zooming in to the interval corresponding to the seventh timestep of ten, all of the displays update to show that interval, where it becomes possible to identify individual communication and synchronization events.

Before using Vampir you need to load the corresponding modules.

```
module load UNITE vampir
```

Important

In order to be able to use `vampir` please make sure you are logged in with

```
ssh -X
```

If you are not directly connected to JUGENE, make sure you are using the `-X` option for all `ssh` connections and that your local system (laptop, PC) has a running X server!

6.1.5.1. Further information

Since a complete description of the Vampir tool is far beyond the scope of this guide, please see the Vampir homepage [<http://vampir.eu/>] for further information.

6.2. Further reading, information and references

JUGENE documentation on the web

- Parallel performance analysis [<http://www.fz-juelich.de/ias/jsc/EN/Expertise/Supercomputers/JUROPA/UserInfo/Performance.html>]
- Scalasca [<http://www.fz-juelich.de/ias/jsc/EN/Expertise/Supercomputers/JUGENE/UserInfo/Scalasca.html>]

General related information

- PAPI homepage [<http://icl.cs.utk.edu/>]
- Scalasca documentation [<http://www.scalasca.org/download/documentation/documentation.html>]
- Scalasca homepage [<http://www.scalasca.org/>]
- TAU homepage [<http://tau.uoregon.edu/>]
- Vampir homepage [<http://vampir.eu/>]

7. Tuning Applications

This sections provides more details information in order to optimize and tune applications for JUGENE.

7.1. Single-core optimization

7.1.1. Advanced compiler options and optimization strategies

For application tuning and code optimization IBM XL compilers will be used as a reference. These compilers offer much more options to optimize code execution on Blue Gene/P system.

7.1.1.1. Advanced compiler flags

Note that aggressive compiler optimizations may result in relaxed conformance to the IEEE floating-point standard, alter the application results or even cause errors in application execution. In this section a detailed discussion of different compiler flags is provided and advanced compiler options are discussed. The options are ordered alphabetically.

-On (n=0, 2, 3, 4, 5)

Compiler optimization includes five base optimization levels (the -O1 option is not supported). The first option -O0 minimizes all the optimization transformations performed by the compiler. It is the most suitable for program-debugging purposes. While it results in a shorter compile time the executables will not show a good performance.

The -O2 option involves strong low-level compiler optimizations. It applies to a unit or subroutine scope and can include function inlining. Almost all programs benefit from this optimization.

At the -O3 optimization level the compiler performs additional low-level transformations. It implies the option -qhot=level=0 which introduces basic high-level analysis and loop transformation. At this level the compiler can perform optimizations that may or may not be beneficial. It should also be noted that the -O3 option implies -qnostrict that can alter floating-point accuracy and therefore the correctness of the program results needs to be checked when using this option.

Further optimizations are introduced with the -O4 option including detailed loop optimization and basic inter-procedural analysis at link time. The most important addition at this level of optimization is the -qipal=level=1 option which activates the interprocedural analysis (IPA). IPA analysis is capable of code optimizations and inlining from one compilation unit to another. To benefit from IPA the -O4 option must be specified in the compilation *and* the link step. IPA based optimizations may result in very long compilation times.

-O5 is the highest XL compiler optimization level. It uses interprocedural analysis at the higher level including the -qipal=level=2 suboption. Note that this level of optimization may consume a lot of machine resources at compile time. The -O5 option should be used only when the application benefits from lower optimization levels and performs as expected.

-qfloat

This option provides control over the compiler optimizations that results in IEEE 754 non-compliant code. To disable certain optimizations proper suboptions should be used. The most common -qfloat suboptions include:

-qfloat=[no]maf will enable or disable combined multiple-add instructions. Sometimes the nomaf suboption must be used to reproduce identical results to those on other architectures. Disabling multiple-add instructions will likely result in significant performance degradation.

-qfloat=[no]rrm controls if round-to-nearest rounding mode is used. The default is norrm.

-qfloat=[no]rsqrt for optimizing the division by the square root with replacing with multiplication by the reciprocal of the square root.

-qfloat=[no]single controls if single-precision arithmetic instructions are used for single-precision floating-point values.

-qfloat=[no]rngchk specifies the range-checking usage for input arguments for software divide and inlined square root operations.

-qfloat=[no]hscmplx enables optimizations on complex division and complex absolute value calculation (disabled by default).

-qhot

High-order transformation (HOT) is a part of the XL compiler devoted to loop transformations. These optimizations are implied by default at the -O4 and -O5 levels. With the -O3 option the -qhot=level=0 suboption is implied. Loop optimization techniques implemented in HOT includes: loop nest interchange, loop fusion, unrolling of loops and data reorganization. -qhot also includes the -qhot=vector suboption for SIMD mode loop execution (vectorization).

-qipal

Interprocedural analysis (IPA) optimization basically operates on the entire program code and tries to apply inter-procedural optimization for the whole program. The IPA mechanism performs transformations at both compile and link time. In order to maximize the benefit the IPA optimizer must be used on both the compile and the link step. IPA may be used on different levels, specifying `-qipa` without a level, or `-O4` will result in `-qipa=level=1`. The `-O5` option applies `-qipa=level=2`. IPA level 0 would reduce compilation time, but performs only a limited analysis.

Other IPA specific suboptions are `-qipa=noobject` in order to generate object files for IPA at link time only, `-qipa=threads` allows additional compilation threads for speed-up the IPA based optimizations, and other options that can be found in the XL compiler reference guide [<http://publib.boulder.ibm.com/infocenter/compgpl/v9v111/index.jsp?topic=/com.ibm.bg9111.doc/bgusing/>].

`-qunroll`

This option controls loop unrolling. It is implied by any optimization level higher than 0. Further suboptions can be specified to control the level of an automatic loop unrolling.

7.1.1.2. Diagnostic compiler flags

Sometimes the compiler is not able to perform certain code optimization or it performs unwanted changes. In order to check what is actually done by the compiler a number of diagnostics can be produced in form of a listing or messages that may guide the user in application tuning and in finding performance bottlenecks.

The diagnostic messages for each subroutine are generally written into a separate file named `name.lst`. This file consists of different sections, depending on the compiler flags used. Some of these sections are:

Header section

One line containing information about the compiler, source file and date and time of compilation.

Options section

Displays the settings for all compiler options that are used in the current compilation step. If the compiler flag `-qlistopt` is used the settings for *all* compiler options are given.

Source section

This section appears only if the `-qsource` flag is used. It contains the source code with line numbers and (if present) the error messages that occurred during compilation.

Loop transformation section

This section appears if the `-qreport` flag is used. It reports if and how loops were transformed by the compiler. It contains valuable information for optimization of the code, for example, whether SIMD vectorization (`-qarch=450d`) of a loop was possible or not, whether loop unrolling has been performed or if the order of loops has been changed.

Object section

This section is created when using the `-qlist` flag and contains the object code listing, which shows the source line number, the instruction offset in hexadecimal notation, the assembler mnemonic of the instruction, and the hexadecimal value of the instruction. On the right side, it also shows the cycle time of the instruction and the intermediate language of the compiler. Finally, the total number of machine instructions that are produced and the total cycle time (straight-line execution time) are displayed. There is a separate section for each compilation unit.

The following options (referring to XL family of compilers) can be used to obtain more information about the changes/optimizations made by the compiler.

`-qflag=<listing_severity>:<terminal_severity>`

Defines the minimum severity level of diagnostic messages to be written to the listing file or to the user terminal. The message severity levels are:

i : informational messages
w : warning messages
e : error, severe error and unrecoverable error messages (C only)
s : severe error and unrecoverable error messages

`-qlist`

The compiler produces a compiler listing that includes an object listing. You can use the object listing to help understand the performance characteristics of the generated code and to diagnose execution problems.

`-qlistopt`

With this option the compiler produces a compiler listing that displays all the options that were in effect when the compiler was invoked.

`-qreport`

The compiler will generate for each source file name `.ext` a file name `.lst` with pseudo code and a description of the kind of code optimizations which were actually performed during compilation.

`-qsource`

The compiler produces a compiler listing that includes source code.

`-qsrcmsg`

This option adds the corresponding source code lines to the diagnostic messages in the `stderr` file.

`-qxflag=diagnostic`

This flag causes the compiler to print information about code optimization during compile time to `stdout`.

`-v`

Instructs the compiler to report information on the progress of the compilation, and names the programs being invoked within the compiler and the options being specified to each program.

As an example, the following Fortran routine `mult` was compiled with compiler diagnostic option `-qreport`.

Example 11. Fortran subroutine `mult`

```
subroutine mult(c,a,ndim)

  implicit none

  integer          :: ndim,i,j
  double precision :: a(ndim),c(ndim,ndim)

  ! Loop
  do i=1,1000
```

```

do j=1,1000
  c(i,j) = a(i)
enddo
enddo

end subroutine mult

```

The loop transformation section in the file `mult.lst` looks as follows:

Example 12. Loop transformation section in `mult.lst`

```

>>>> LOOP TRANSFORMATION SECTION <<<<<
  1|          SUBROUTINE mult (c, a, ndim)
  1|          $.CSE0 = ndim
 10|          IF (.FALSE.) THEN
          $.LoopIV0 = 0
      Id=5      DO $.LoopIV0 = $.LoopIV0, 1844674
 11|          IF (.FALSE.) GOTO lab_40
          $.LoopIV1 = 0
 12|          $.ICM0 = $.CSE0
          $.CSE1 = max($.CSE0,0)
          $.ICM1 = $.CSE1
          $.ICM2 = ($.CSE1 * (-8) - 8)
          $.ICM3 = ($.LoopIV0 + 1)
          $.ICM4 = ($.CSE1 * 8)
 11| Id=6      DO $.LoopIV1 = $.LoopIV1, 999
          ! DIR_INDEPENDENT loopId = 0
          ! DIR_INDEPENDENT loopId = 0
 12|          $.CSE2 = ($.LoopIV1 + 1)
          c($.CSE2,$.ICM3) = a($.CSE2)
 13|          ENDDO
          lab_40
 14|          ENDDO
          ENDIF
 10|          IF (.FALSE.) GOTO lab_9
          $.CIV2 = 0
      Id=1      DO $.CIV2 = $.CIV2, 499
 11|          IF (.FALSE.) GOTO lab_11
          $.LoopIV1 = 0
 12|          $.ICM0 = $.CSE0
          $.CSE3 = max($.CSE0,0)
          $.ICM1 = $.CSE3
          $.ICM2 = ($.CSE3 * (-8) - 8)
          $.CSE4 = ($.CIV2 * 2)
          $.ICM5 = ($.CSE4 + 1)
          $.ICM4 = ($.CSE3 * 8)
          $.ICM6 = ($.CSE4 + 2)
 11| Id=2      DO $.LoopIV1 = $.LoopIV1, 999
          ! DIR_INDEPENDENT loopId = 0
          ! DIR_INDEPENDENT loopId = 0
 12|          $.CSE5 = ($.LoopIV1 + 1)
          $.CSE6 = a($.CSE5)
          c($.CSE5,$.ICM5) = $.CSE6
          c($.CSE5,$.ICM6) = $.CSE6
 13|          ENDDO
          lab_11

```

```

14 |          ENDDO
    |          lab_9
16 |          RETURN
    |          END SUBROUTINE mult
Source File      Source Line      Loop Id      Action / Information
-----
          0          10          1 Loop interchanging
          0          10          1 Outer loop has been
                                applied to loop nest
                                unrolled 2 time(s)

```

This indicates that a loop interchanging has been performed (inner loop is now `id=2`) and that the outer loop has been unrolled 2 times (`id=1`).

For further information about diagnostic compiler flags, please see the IBM documentation [http://publib.boulder.ibm.com/infocenter/comphelp/v111v131/index.jsp?topic=%2Fcom.ibm.xlf131.aix.doc%2Fcompiler_ref%2Fparlist.html]

7.1.1.3. Making efficient use of the double FPU ("double hummer")

To make use of the double FPU unit (450d mode) within the BlueGene/P compute processor user applications must meet the following general guidelines and requirements. Because the double FPU is capable of operating on vector data in SIMD mode (Single Instruction Multiple Data mode), selected parts of program code (loops in particular) are often said to be *vectorized*.

Use compiler options to generate SIMD code

Only the XL family of compilers offers support for double FPU, thus all the information in this section refer to XL C or XL Fortran compilers only. Two different sets of compiler options could generate code for double FPU (SIMD instructions):

- default `-qarch=450d` option together with `-O3`
- high-order optimization `-O4`, `-O5` options or `-qhot` with more specific `-qhot=simd` (valid only with `-qarch=450d` option)

Proper data alignment

Using double FPU requires data to be 16-byte aligned. It means that program data structures (arrays, structs, etc.) must be placed in memory with addresses being a multiple of 16 bytes. Normally XL compilers try to allocate the data with proper alignment. For some cases it may not be sufficient. You may look for SIMD problems related to improper alignment in the compiler listing (`.lst`) file. To have a listing file generated, use `-qreport -qlist` option on the compile command (see Section 7.1.1.2).

If the compiler failed to align the data for SIMD execution you may need to use alignment assertions (for `a` being an array):

- `__alignx(16, a)` in C
 - `call alignx(16, a(1))` in Fortran
- These assertion intrinsics are supported by XL compilers only.

Checking if Double FPU is used

To ensure that the compilers have generated SIMD instructions, one may examine the compiler listing file. Compile your program with the `-qlist -qsource` options (see Section 7.1.1.2) to include the assembler listing in the file. The complete list of SIMD assembler instructions for

double FPU can be found in the IBM Redbook for "IBM System Blue Gene Solution: Blue Gene/P Application Development" RedBook AD.

If any of these instructions appear in a listing file, then at least some part of the program is using the double FPU. For example, the following line in the .lst file:

```
46| 000640 fpmadd    00611020    1      FPMADD    fp3,fp35=fp2,fp34,\
                                     fp1,fp33,fp0,fp32,\
                                     fcr
```

indicates that `fpmadd` instruction for SIMD fused-multiply-add is used.

You may also use `-qreport` option on the compile command to see additional information regarding SIMD optimizations performed by the compiler (see Section 7.1.1.2).

Using SIMD intrinsics routines

Another method of exploiting the double FPU is to use SIMD compiler intrinsics. These are direct equivalents for SIMD assembler instructions discussed earlier, supported by XL compiler family. Functions used for elementary SIMD arithmetic operations are callable from both C and Fortran. Again, for more information refer to the IBM Redbook RedBook AD.

Optimized SIMD library routines

The Blue Gene/P system offers mathematical libraries optimized for the double FPU. This is often the easiest way of making efficient use of double FPU. For more information on SIMD libraries see the ESSL library.

Other issues that influence SIMD execution

Many more factors may inhibit generation of SIMD instructions and furthermore lower the performance of the application. Typical issues that should be avoided are: *non-stride data access, loops with subroutine/function calls, many-branch or conditional instructions, pointer aliasing, non-trivial data dependencies*. Some of these issues can be detected by the compiler. Use the `-qreport` option (see Section 7.1.1.2) in the compile command and examine the listing file for potential SIMD related issues.

7.1.1.4. Optimization strategies

In this section we provide some optimization strategies for serial code performance with the help of examples.

Consider the following example of a basic Fortran program that multiplies two square double-precision matrices. The program uses the direct method of matrix multiplications with two nested loops and third inner implicitly nested loop (with use of the `:` operator in Fortran).

Example 13. Matrix multiplication in Fortran

```
program mat_mul
  Implicit None

  Integer, parameter :: n = 1024
  Real*8 :: a(n,n), b(n,n), c(n,n)
  Real*8 :: alf
  Real :: timef, time1, time0
  Integer :: i, j
```

```

call mat_init(a, b, c, n)
time0 = timef()
Do i = 1,n
  Do j = 1,n
    c(i,j) = sum(a(i,:)*b(:,j))
  End Do
End Do
time1 = timef()
write(0,'(A,F12.9,A)') 'mat_mul in ',0.001*(time1-time0),&
&      ' seconds'

call mat_cmp(c, n)

end program mat_mul

```

The optimization strategy is to execute the loops in SIMD mode with using the double FPU. In order to measure the execution time, the `timef()` intrinsic XL Fortran function is used. This function returns the actual time in milliseconds. Only time spent in the loops is measured. Additional external subroutines are used for initializing the matrices (`mat_init`) and further computation (`mat_cmp`).

- *Basic compiler optimization*

Compile with the basic optimization options for BlueGene/P processor:

```
bgxlf_r -O2 -qtune=450 -qarch=450 -o mat_mul.exe mat_mul.f90
```

and run the `mat_mul.exe` program on a processor core. Time spent in main loops should be as follows:

```
mat_mul in 70.269523621 seconds
```

which gives about 30.5 Mflops being below 1% of theoretical peak performance of a processor core.

- *More compiler optimization*

Change optimization level from `-O2` to `-O3` and add `-qstrict` option to avoid numerical differences caused by aggressive code optimization:

```
bgxlf_r -O3 -qstrict -qtune=450 -qarch=450 ...
```

The result is 52.3 seconds.

- *Automatic SIMD code generation*

Switch to `-qarch=450d` option to turn on SIMD instructions compiler generation for the loops:

```
bgxlf_r -O3 -qstrict -qtune=450 -qarch=450d ...
```

Time result is 60.05 seconds which is even worse than the previous setting.

- *Cache friendly loop ordering*

One of the reasons for inefficient SIMD usage is data access which is not cache aware. Matrices in Fortran are stored in memory column-by-column and loop order should also maximize column based data access. Code with reordered loops for matrix multiplication may look as in the following example:

Example 14. Cache-friendly matrix multiplication in Fortran

```

program mat_mul
  Implicit None

  Integer, parameter :: n = 1024
  Real*8 :: a(n,n), b(n,n), c(n,n)
  Real*8 :: alf
  Real :: timef, time1, time0
  Integer :: i, j

  call mat_init(a, b, c, n)
  time0 = timef()
  Do j = 1,n
    Do k = 1,n
      Do i = 1,n
        c(i,j) = c(i,j) + a(i,k)*b(k,j)
      End Do
    End Do
  End Do

  time1 = timef()
  write(0,'(A,F12.9,A)') 'mat_mul in ',0.001*(time1-time0),&
&      ' seconds'

  call mat_cmp(c, n)

end program mat_mul

```

Note that the sum function is no longer used and third nested loop is explicitly introduced. Moreover loop order is changed from i-j to j-k-i.

Leave the `-qarch=450d` option turned on for compilation:

```
bgxlf_r -O3 -qstrict -qtune=450 -qarch=450d ...
```

Run the code:

```
mat_mul in 3.469617128 seconds
```

Note the dramatical change in a program runtime! This will give roughly 619 Mflops.

- *High order transformations*

One could try compilation with high order compiler transformation (`-qhot` option):

```
bgxlf_r -O3 -qhot -qstrict -qtune=450 -qarch=450d ...
```

which is not beneficial with this case:

```
mat_mul in 7.878117085 seconds
```

A more inquiring user may notice that the `-qhot` option results in BLAS `dgemm` routine substitution for original triple loop. Compile with an option `-qreport -qlist` to produce compiler listing which will be placed in `.lst` file. Open the listing file to see the compiler-optimized code:

```

23|          $.__x1_matmul__ALPHA_10 = 1.0000000000000000E+000
      $.__x1_matmul__BETA_00 = 1.0000000000000000E+000
      $.__x1_matmul__transab_N0 = 78

```

```

$.__xl_matmul__I0 = 1024
$.__xl_matmul__J0 = 1024
$.__xl_matmul__K0 = 1024
$.__xl_matmul__LDA0 = 1024
$.__xl_matmul__LDB0 = 1024
$.__xl_matmul__LDC0 = 1024
CALL __xl_dgemm($.__xl_matmul__transab_N0,&
& $.__xl_matmul__transab_N0,$.__xl_matmul__I0,\
$.__xl_matmul__J0,&
& $.__xl_matmul__K0,$.__xl_matmul__ALPHA_10,0 + a,&
& $.__xl_matmul__LDA0,0 + b,$.__xl_matmul__LDB0,&
& $.__xl_matmul__BETA_00,0 + c,$.__xl_matmul__LDC0)

```

That means the compiler is capable of recognizing the matrix multiplication code pattern and tries to use theoretically the most optimized solution. The problem is that the XL compiler intrinsic BLAS library call (`__xl_dgemm`) is not as optimal as it could be.

In the listing file you may also find some messages about SIMD optimization:

```

1586-551 (I) Loop (loop index 9) at mat_mul.f90 <line 16> was not\
SIMD vectorized because it contains unsupported vector data types.
1586-542 (I) Loop (loop index 10 with nest-level 1 and iteration \
count 1024) at mat_mul.f90 <line 15> was SIMD vectorized.
1586-543 (I) <SIMD info> Total number of the innermost loops\
considered <"5">. Total number of the innermost loops SIMD\
vectorized <"2">.

```

These information may guide you to the more SIMD optimized version of your code.

- *Use SIMD intrinsics*

Another step to increase the level of the double FPU usage may be introducing the SIMD intrinsic functions for elementary arithmetic operations. This probably needs a significant amount of work. Moreover it may require the advanced knowledge in processor programming.

The list of XL compiler SIMD intrinsic functions may be found in the IBM Redbook for "IBM System Blue Gene Solution: Blue Gene/P Application Development" RedBook AD.

In this book you may find the SIMD Fortran routine for double-precision square matrix-matrix multiplication. Look for the example 8-19 in page 136, the routine name is `dsqmm`. You can copy it into your program and call directly instead of the triple loop. Compile the modified program for double FPU:

```
bgxlf_r -O3 -qstrict -qtune=450 -qarch=450d ...
```

It can be easily seen that SIMD optimization was still profitable - the program is twice as fast with a performance of 1267.64 Mflops:

```
dsqmm in 1.694082141 seconds
```

- *Use optimized SIMD math library*

Often the most effective way to lever up the performance is to use the highly optimized SIMD library. On the JUGENE system the most optimized mathematical library is the IBM ESSL library. It contains the extended BLAS functions functionality for optimized linear algebra.

To use BLAS routine for matrix multiplication (double-precision general case: `dgemm`) one needs to modify the example as follows:

Example 15. DGEMM matrix multiplication in Fortran

```
program mat_mul
  Implicit None

  Integer, parameter :: n = 1024
  Real*8 :: a(n,n), b(n,n), c(n,n)
  Real*8 :: alf
  Real :: timef, time1, time0
  Integer :: i, j
  Character :: transa

  External dgemm

  call mat_init(a, b, c, n)

  transa = 'N'
  alf = 1.0
  time0 = timef()

  call dgemm(transa,transa,n,n,n,alf,a,n,b,n,alf,d,n)

  time1 = timef()
  write(0,'(A,F12.9,A)') 'dgemm in ',0.001*(time1-time0),&
&      ' seconds'

  call mat_cmp(c, n)

  end program mat_mul
```

Leave the compilation options unchanged, recompile and run the program:

```
dgemm in 7.894634247 seconds
```

Note that the result is exactly the same as with the compiler BLAS substitution. The same (not optimal) compiler intrinsic version of the library was used.

In order to use ESSL library you need to link your program with `-lesslbg` option. On the JUGENE the ESSL library is located in `/opt/ibmmath/essl/4.4/lib` directory. Recompile the code with correct linking options:

```
bgxlf_r -O3 -qstrict -qtune=450 -qarch=450d -o mat_mul.exe
mat_mul.f90 -L/opt/ibmmath/essl/4.4/lib -lesslbg
```

Run the BLAS and ESSL version to measure the performance:

```
dgemm in 0.831952870 seconds
```

The performance is doubled again! We have reached 2581.26 Mflops which is about 75% of the peak performance.

7.2. Advanced environment and MPI tuning

7.2.1. Environment variables

Here we list some environment variables (in alphabetical order) which can be used in order to tune the performance of applications. A more comprehensive list of available Blue Gene/P MPI environment variables can be found in the Blue Gene/P Application Development Redbook RedBook AD.

`BG_COREDUMPDISABLED`

Defines whether core dumps are generated or not in case the application aborts due to an error. The default is 1 (no core dumps are generated). To enable the generation of core dumps set this variable to 0 (see Section 8.3 for further information).

`BGLMPIO_COMM`

This environment variable defines how data is exchanged on collective reads and writes. Possible values are 0 (use `MPI_Alltoallv`) and 1 (use `MPI_Isend/MPI_Irecv`). The default is 0. When using a large number of tasks in a memory-demanding application the performance of the `MPI_Alltoallv` might scale worse than the point-to-point version for the I/O or the application might even crash with a `signal 6`. Setting this variable to 1 might help in this case and improve the performance (see also `BGLMPIO_TUNEBLOCKING=0`).

`BGLMPIO_TUNEBLOCKING`

This variable can be used to tune how aggregate file domains are calculated. Possible values are 0 (Evenly calculate file domains across aggregators, also use `MPI_Isend/MPI_Irecv` to exchange domain information) and 1 (Align file domains with the underlying file system's block size, also use `MPI_Alltoallv` to exchange domain information). The default is 1. This variable can be used together with the `BGLMPIO_COMM` variable (see above), for example, `BGLMPIO_COMM=1` and `BGLMPIO_TUNEBLOCKING=0` to avoid `MPI_Alltoallv`.

`DCMF_ALLTOALL_PREMALLOC`

The `ALLTOALL` MPI protocols (`ALLTOALL`, `ALLTOALLV` AND `ALLTOALLW`) require 6 arrays each of size `COMM_SIZE` to be setup before communication begins. If your application does not use `ALLTOALL` or needs as much memory as possible you can turn off pre-allocating these arrays by setting the variable to `N`. The default setting is `Y`, which means allowing the pre-allocation.

`DCMF_DMA_VERBOSE`

Use this variable to control the output of information associated with the Direct Memory Access (DMA) messaging device. Possible values are 0 (no DMA information output) and 1 (DMA information output). The default is 0. If the job encounters events that do not cause the application to fail but might be useful for application developers (for example RAS Events) this information will be displayed by setting `DCMF_DMA_VERBOSE=1`. When using the option `-verbose 2` with the `mpirun` command this variable is automatically set to 1.

`DCMF_EAGER=message size (bytes)`

This environment variable sets the message size (in bytes) above which the MPI rendezvous protocol is used (for further details about the MPI protocols available, please see the Blue Gene/P Application Development Redbook RedBook AD). The default size is 1200 bytes. The MPI rendezvous protocol is optimized for maximum bandwidth. However, there is an initial handshake between the communication partners, which increases the latency. In case your application uses many short messages you might want to decrease the message size (even down to 0). On the other hand if your application can be mapped well to the TORUS network and uses mainly large messages increasing the limit might lead to a better performance (for example, `DCMF_EAGER=200000`).

`DCMF_INTERRUPT`

If set to 1 the interrupt driven communication is turned on. This can be beneficial to some applications in order to overlap communication with computation and is required if you are using Global Arrays or ARMCI. The default setting is 0.

```
DCMF_RECFFIFO=buffer size (bytes)
```

Packets that arrive off the network are placed into a reception buffer. The environment variable DCMF_RECFFIFO can be used to set the size of this buffer. The default size is 8 MB per process. If a process is busy and does not call often enough MPI_Wait this buffer can become full and the movement of further packets is stopped until the buffer is free again. This can slow down the application. In this case the buffer should be increased.

```
DCMF_RGETFFIFO=buffer size (bytes)
```

When a remote get packet arrives off the network, the packet contains a descriptor describing data that is to be retrieved and sent back to the node that originated the remote get packet. The DMA injects that descriptor into a remote get injection buffer. The DMA then processes that injected descriptor by sending the data back to the originating node. Remote gets are commonly done during point-to-point communications when large data buffers are involved (typically larger than 1200 bytes). DCMF_RGETFFIFO can be used to set the size of the buffer. The default size is 32 KB. When a large number of remote get packets are received by a node, the remote get injection buffer may become full of descriptors. The size of the buffer can be adjusted using DCMF_RGETFFIFO.

```
DCMF_SSM
```

Setting this variable to 1 turns on sender-side matching and can speed up point-to-point messaging in well-behaved applications. The default setting is 0.

7.2.2. Network

The choice of the network (connection) can have a big influence on the performance of applications. The Blue Gene/P offers two networks which can be used by applications for the communication on and between compute nodes. The TORUS network interconnects all compute nodes and has a topology of a three-dimensional torus, that means each node has six nearest neighbours. The MESH network is a global collective tree network. It interconnects all compute and I/O nodes.

The default network is the MESH network. You can change it using the LoadLeveler keyword `#@bg_connection` specifying either MESH, PREFER_TORUS or TORUS as shown in the following example:

Example 16. Specifying the network with `#@bg_connection`

```
#@job_name = Job_example
#@comment = "BGP Job with torus network"
#@job_type = bluegene
...
#@bg_connection = TORUS
...
#@queue
```

The example shows part of a job script for using the torus network. The choice can have a big influence on the performance of your application. In case of doubt choose TORUS. For partitions with less than 512 nodes only MESH can be used.

Tip

In general applications benefit using the TORUS network. Therefore, it is recommended to use `#@bg_connection = TORUS`.

7.2.3. Shape

The extension of a partition in X,Y and Z direction is called the shape $X \times Y \times Z$ of a partition. The shape can be specified in units of midplanes using the LoadLeveler keyword `#@bg_shape`, where 1 midplane contains 512 nodes (=2048 cores):

Example 17. Specifying the shape with `#@bg_shape`

```
#@job_name = Shape_example
#@comment = "BGP Job by Shape"
#@job_type = bluegene
#@bg_connection = TORUS
...
#@bg_shape = 1x1x2
#@bg_rotate = TRUE
...
#@queue
```

This job script reserves a partition with 1 midplane in X and Y, and 2 midplanes in Z direction using in total 1024 nodes (4096 cores). The keyword `#@bg_rotate` tells LoadLeveler whether the job can run on any partition with the correct size (TRUE, this is the default) or if you want to have exactly the specified shape (FALSE). In the first case the next free partition with 1024 nodes will be used, regardless of its shape (for example, a partition of shape $2 \times 1 \times 1$ could be used). The optimal shape for an application depends on the communication pattern of the code. For example, if the application uses a communicator of dimensions $8 \times 8 \times 32$ a shape like $1 \times 1 \times 2$ might show a better performance than for example $2 \times 1 \times 1$. For further information, please see also Section 7.2.4.

If you use partition sizes of 1 midplane or less on JUGENE the partitions will have the dimensions NX,NY, and NZ in units of nodes (32 nodes is the smallest size you can reserve on JUGENE) as shown in Table 16.

Table 16. Dimensions in units of nodes in NX, NY and NZ directions for partitions with up to 512 nodes on JUGENE.

Number of nodes	NX	NY	NZ
32	4	4	2
64	4	4	4
128	4	4	8
256	8	4	8
512	8	8	8

7.2.4. Mapping

The default mapping on JUGENE is in XYZT order. Here, X,Y and Z are the torus coordinates of the compute nodes within a partition and T is the core coordinate within a node (T=0,1,2,3). Therefore, each core is well-defined by these four coordinates. When `mpirun` launches a parallel application it will distribute the MPI tasks in such a way that the first coordinate of the mapping is increased first. Therefore, with XYZT mapping the first MPI task is executed on the core with the coordinates (0,0,0,0), the second on the core (1,0,0,0), the third on the core 2,0,0,0 and so on. Since in general adjacent tasks are not executed on adjacent cores, this might not be the optimal mapping for all applications. You can change the mapping using the `-mapfile` option of the `mpirun` command.

```
mpirun -mapfile mapping -exe myproc
```

mapping can either be any permutation of X,Y,Z and T or a file which contains explicit instructions on how to map the MPI tasks to the cores.

Tip

Since for most applications the default mapping XYZT is not optimal, we recommend testing at least the option `-mapfile TXYZ`.

7.2.4.1. Explicit mapfiles

An explicit mapping of tasks to cores can be specified using a mapfile. Each line of such a file contains four integers which represent coordinates of the four-dimensional torus in the order X, Y, Z and T. The tasks are mapped to the specified coordinates in ascending order (see example below). The optimal mapping depends on the communicator used by the application and the shape of the partition used for the run. Therefore, it is not possible to choose an optimal mapping without detailed knowledge about the application. In order to describe the strategy to follow we discuss an example case.

Suppose we have an application which uses a three-dimensional communicator of dimensions $16 \times 16 \times 8$ which should run on one midplane in VN mode (that means a four-dimensional torus of shape $X \times Y \times Z \times T = 8 \times 8 \times 8 \times 4$). The goal is to factorize the shape dimensions by choosing a corresponding mapping in such a way that it fits to the communicator of the application. In this case $(X \times T / 2) \times (Y \times T / 2) \times Z = 16 \times 16 \times 8$ would be optimal. The following mapfile (only shown in parts) realizes the described mapping (everything after "#" is only a comment):

```
0 0 0 0 # task 0; communicator coordinates ( 0, 0, 0)
1 0 0 0 # task 1; communicator coordinates ( 1, 0, 0)
2 0 0 0 # task 2; communicator coordinates ( 2, 0, 0)
...
7 0 0 0 # task 7; communicator coordinates ( 7, 0, 0)
0 0 0 1 # task 8; communicator coordinates ( 8, 0, 0)
1 0 0 1 # task 9; communicator coordinates ( 9, 0, 0)
...
7 0 0 1 # task 15; communicator coordinates (15, 0, 0)
0 1 0 0 # task 16; communicator coordinates ( 0, 1, 0)
1 1 0 0 # task 17; communicator coordinates ( 1, 1, 0)
...
7 1 0 0 # task 23; communicator coordinates ( 7, 1, 0)
0 1 0 1 # task 24; communicator coordinates ( 8, 1, 0)
1 1 0 1 # task 25; communicator coordinates ( 9, 1, 0)
...
...
0 0 0 2 # task 64; communicator coordinates ( 0, 8, 0)
1 0 0 2 # task 65; communicator coordinates ( 1, 8, 0)
2 0 0 2 # task 66; communicator coordinates ( 2, 8, 0)
...
7 0 0 2 # task 71; communicator coordinates ( 7, 8, 0)
0 0 0 3 # task 72; communicator coordinates ( 8, 8, 0)
1 0 0 3 # task 73; communicator coordinates ( 9, 8, 0)
...
```

When using explicit mapfile you must use the LoadLeveler keyword `#@bg_rotate=FALSE` in your job script.

7.3. Advanced OpenMP usage

The Blue Gene/P compute node architecture offers very few opportunities for advanced OpenMP features. Here are a few elements one can consider when running an OpenMP or a hybrid MPI + OpenMP code on Blue Gene/P.

7.3.1. Environment variables

Besides `OMP_NUM_THREADS`, one environment variable is really worth mentioning here: `XLSMPOPTS`. This one is useful when the code needs a large stack for running. OpenMP uses a per-thread private stack that is by default limited to 4 MB. But this might be insufficient for some codes that require a larger stack for storing automatic variables.

To set the per-thread stack size to the desired value, one can for example use:

```
mpirun -env "XLSMPOPTS=stack=6000000" ...
```

This will set it to a per-thread value of 6000000 bytes.

For OpenMP codes compiled using the GNU compiler version 4.3.2 onward, one can use the environment variable `GOMP_STACKSIZE` to achieve the same result. The given number represents the per-thread desired stack size in bytes. It can be set for example like this:

```
mpirun -env "GOMP_STACKSIZE=6000000" ...
```

7.3.2. Thread affinity

Affinity is a concept that is not supported on Blue Gene/P. There is therefore no point in trying to set it for multi-threaded codes.

7.4. Hybrid programming

The Blue Gene/P machine is first and foremost a massively parallel architecture. It is primarily designed for running as large as possible MPI parallel codes. In addition, its back-end nodes allowing shared memory parallel programming like OpenMP, it seems like a natural solution to use hybrid MPI+OpenMP parallel codes.

The main advantages of such an approach are:

- To increase the per-MPI task available memory without wasting the corresponding CPU capacity. By using the DUAL or SMP mode rather than the VN (virtual node) one, one can double or quadruple the amount of memory available for each MPI task. However, if a second level of intra-node parallelization is not introduced in the code, only one of the two or four cores of the node will be exploited. Adding OpenMP directives to your MPI code might solve this issue.
- To reduce the number of MPI tasks without reducing the number of involved CPUs. The parallel design or scalability of some codes is inherently limited by a maximum of possible MPI tasks. By allowing for a given number of such tasks to run on a two to four time larger number of cores, one can push this limit further without sacrificing the code's efficiency.

This hybrid MPI+OpenMP approach proved being very successful on many architectures, including Blue Gene/P.

7.4.1. Optimal tasks / threads strategy

For defining the optimal tasks versus threads strategy, one has to understand that the Blue Gene/P compute nodes do not allow for more user processes or threads running on a node than the number of available cores. Moreover, as described in Section 5.4.2, OpenMP can be enabled on back-end nodes with only either SMP or DUAL mode.

In those conditions, the number of OpenMP threads to use set with `OMP_NUM_THREADS` can only be *1, 2, 3 or 4* for SMP mode and *1 or 2* for DUAL mode.

Actually the only reason for running an OpenMP code in a configuration other than DUAL mode with `OMP_NUM_THREADS=2` or SMP mode with `OMP_NUM_THREADS=4` would be if the available memory was insufficient for running with all the possible threads. This might happen if for example the private stack size needed by each OpenMP thread is especially large and doesn't allow all the threads to fit in memory.

In this very unlikely case only, having `OMP_NUM_THREADS` set to 2 or 3 rather than 4 in SMP mode, or set to 1 in DUAL mode might be necessary to solve the issue.

7.5. I/O optimization

This section briefly mentions general guidelines for efficient I/O on JUGENE and subsequently presents readily available tools that can be of help in separate subsections. A general understanding of the structure of JUGENE's I/O subsystem and the organization of its file system as documented in this guide in Section 2.6 and Section 2.7 is assumed.

7.5.1. General guidelines

7.5.1.1. Using the right file system

The scratch file system (`WORK`), accessed by means of the shell environment variable `$WORK`, is the file system of choice for jobs with demanding I/O. Direct reading or writing of files on the `HOME` file system is reasonable only for jobs that structurally use rather small sized I/O request - this means less than 4 MB per read or write action.

7.5.1.2. Adhere to block size and pay attention to block alignment

As with most file systems, I/O operations on `WORK` as well as `HOME` are most efficient when the request sizes are exact multiples of the file system's block size and kept well aligned with file system block boundaries. The block size for the `WORK` file system is 4 MB. The block size for the `HOME` file systems is 1 MB. Users that want to avoid the hard coding of block sizes can use the standard POSIX function `stat()`, or `fstat()` in the initialization phase of their application. The field `st_blksize` of the returned `stat` structure contains the block size of the file system in bytes.

The primary focus of special libraries for parallel I/O, such as parallel HDF5 or parallel netCDF is on organizing output into portable platform independent formats. Doing efficient I/O is to some extent delegated to these libraries by using their routines, but it is not their primary concern. These libraries are built on top of MPI I/O. MPI I/O can be "hinted", rather than instructed, to be more efficient by using `MPI_info` key value pairs to specify desired buffer size, stripe size, etc.

7.5.1.3. Optimize hierarchical I/O schemes by distributing the load over all available I/O nodes

I/O operations that stripe over a larger number of blocks are more efficient, because they are capable of utilizing more of the underlying storage resources in parallel. But they are costly in terms of buffer memory needed in user space and may prove difficult to organize on an architecture like the Blue Gene/P that offers a fairly limited amount of memory per task. If such a hierarchical scheme, where presumably a subset of the tasks is doing large I/O operations, is implemented on JUGENE, it should be optimized to spread the work well over all I/O nodes available to the job. IBM's implementation of MPI contains two Blue Gene/P specific extensions that were added for this purpose: `MPIX_Pset_same_comm_create()` and `MPIX_Psetdiff_comm_create()` (see Section 5.3.1.4). Both are collective operations that create a set of communicators, of which each node only sees the one that corresponds to its place in the topology. The first call creates communicators for every Pset that contain only the members of the Pset. All I/O nodes are used if, for example, every node 0 in these communicators takes the role of a master node for the rest of the nodes. The second call creates a set of orthogonal communicators in which no two members of a given communicator belong to the same Pset.

7.5.1.4. Consider not to use a hierarchical scheme

The same efficiency that is associated with striping over a large number of file system blocks can in principle also be achieved by a large number of parallel tasks engaging in operations on the same file, each on its own fairly small number of blocks. The tasks must be orchestrated to operate on distinct file system blocks rather than operate on - from the perspective of file system organization - arbitrary

ranges of a file that overlap in file system block usage. If all tasks are involved, doing I/O themselves, all I/O nodes are involved as well. However, task-local files must be avoided since handling of thousands of individual files can cause a severe performance bottleneck (see Section 7.5.1.5 for further information).

SIONlib (Section 7.5.5) which is a library that is currently being developed at Jülich, may be a helpful tool for automating the organization of an I/O along these lines.

7.5.1.5. Revise I/O of ported applications if its design assumes node local storage

Applications ported from "Beowulf" clusters and other architectures that typically have node local scratch space often have an organization of I/O in which all task specific data - intermediate states kept for checkpointing, error logs, final output data - are written to task specific files stored on local storage for scratch. On these architectures this is indeed a fairly straightforward and efficient way of making use of all the distributed I/O resources that the platform has allocated to the job. On JUGENE it is not, since there is no distributed node local scratch space. Trivial adaptations of the application's I/O organization, that simply keep the multitude of task specific files and merely solve possible filename conflicts that can occur because the scratch file system on this platform has a global name space, lead to other severe performance issues. A multitude of directories and/or files must be created in the startup phase of a job, typically under a common root in the file system. This leads to severe "hot spots" in meta-data handling, and thus to congestion and severe slowdown for the job - possibly even to slowdown of the I/O of unrelated jobs that experience delay from the busy meta-data servers. Revise such I/O schemes by an alternative that better fits JUGENE's architecture, for example, a hierarchical scheme referred to in Section 7.5.1.3, or a non-hierarchical scheme, referred to in Section 7.5.1.4.

7.5.2. HDF5

The HDF5 Library is available on JUGENE and can be loaded with

```
module load hdf5
```

Further information about how to use it on JUGENE can be obtained with

```
module help hdf5  
news hdf5
```

Further information about HDF5 are available at the HDF group [<http://www.hdfgroup.org/HDF5/>].

7.5.3. MPI I/O

MPI I/O is a substandard of MPI specifically for dealing with parallel I/O. It offers routines that implement the opening, reading, writing, and closing of files as collective actions. It is generic and flexible. Both hierarchical and non-hierarchical schemes are feasibly implemented by means of MPI I/O. It also offers routines collective and non-collective handling of files that haven been opened collectively.

MPI I/O introduces its own data types. MPI files are lists of MPI datatypes. Basic types are pre-defined. Derived types can be tailored to suit the application's needs. MPI I/O is available on other platforms as well and files written by MPI I/O are portable between different platforms. Usage of MPI I/O however does not automatically tune file system access. The data types of MPI I/O mainly make sense to the application, but are not necessarily well aligned with respect to file system specific parameters.

Parallel versions of netCDF and HDF are built on top of MPI I/O to enable parallel file access.

7.5.4. netCDF

Versions 3.6.3 and 4.1.1 of netCDF are installed on JUGENE. Currently, no module is available, but you can find the libraries on JUGENE at

```
/bgsys/local/netcdf
```

Documentation can be found in

```
/bgsys/local/netcdf/v3.6.3/share  
/bgsys/local/netcdf/v4.1.1/share/doc/netcdf
```

Further information about netCDF are available here [<http://www.unidata.ucar.edu/software/netcdf/>].

7.5.5. SIONlib

SIONlib is a small library that focuses primarily on tuning massive parallel file access to the underlying storage system. It uses MPI to manage opening and closing of files as collective actions with standard POSIX I/O routines. It does not introduce its own datatypes. Rather it takes the traditional Unix view that for the I/O routines a file is a generic stream of binary data. Thus its introduction into existing source code is not very intrusive. By replacing a limited number of I/O calls by SIONlib alternatives that internally take care of the orchestration of block size alignment, the tuning of massive parallel I/O operations to the underlying file system is significantly improved.

Several versions of SIONLib are available on JUGENE. You can manage which one you want to use by means of environment modules. To use the default version simply enter:

```
module load sionlib
```

To see which versions are available enter `module avail sionlib`, and pick the version that suits you best.

The module command puts SIONlib tools like `sioncat`, `siondump`, and `sionsplit`, in your search path. These are for extracting data from a sion file, dumping its meta data, and splitting a sion files into separate ones. But most importantly this also puts the `sionconfig` tool into your search path. Use this tool to obtain the correct values for the include files and libraries that you need.

We assume usage of the IBM compiler by means of the `mpixlc_r` C compiler compiler wrapper script. To obtain the correct compiler switches for parallel I/O using SIONlib on JUGENE, use the `sionconfig` tool as follows: `sionconfig --be --mpi --cflags`. The "--be" denotes the BlueGene "Back End" architecture as a target to generate code for, as opposed to the "Front End" (--fe) node architecture of the login nodes. The `sionconfig` tool thus used produces something like the following - with path details depending on the version - `-I/usr/local/sionlib/v1.2p2/include -DBGP -DSION_MPI -D_SION_BGP` which can be used in your Makefile or build script.

To obtain the correct switches for the linking of objects with libraries use: `sionconfig --be --mpi --libs` This produces something like the following - with path details depending on the version - `-L/usr/local/sionlib/v1.2p2/lib -lsion_32 -lsionser_32`

Thus, the following example would compile a file `mysource1.c` to `mysource1.o` and subsequently link that object file with the SIONlib libraries to produce the executable binary `mybinary1`.

```
mpixlc_r -I/usr/local/sionlib/v1.2p2/include -DBGP -DSION_MPI\  
-D_SION_BGP -c source1.c  
mpixlc_r -o mybinary1 source1.o -L/usr/local/sionlib/v1.2p2/lib\  
-lsion_32 -lsionser_32
```

Further information about SIONlib are available at the SIONlib site [<http://www.fz-juelich.de/jsc/sionlib/>].

7.6. Advanced job command language

7.6.1. Using multiple job steps

The LoadLeveler batch system allows users to create and control the execution of more complex jobs. Users may define a sequence of job steps which may possibly depend on each other. For each of the job steps a correspondent LoadLeveler keyword block must be defined in the job command file. A job step keyword block must begin with the `#@step_name` keyword which defines the name of the step and must contain the `#@queue` keyword. LoadLeveler will execute all job steps as independent jobs unless the keyword `#@dependency` is used. Dependency means that a job step execution will be started depending on the status of the previous job step.

Example 18. Job command file with multiple steps

```

#@job_name = example_multiple_steps
#@environment = COPY_ALL
#@notification = error
#@notify_user = my_address@my.institution
#@job_type = bluegene
#@bg_size = 32
#
#@step_name = step_1
#@error = step_1.err
#@output = step_1.out
#@queue
#
#@step_name = step_2
#@dependency = (step_1 == 0)
#@error = step_2.err
#@output = step_2.out
#@queue
#
#@step_name = step_3
#@error = step_3.err
#@output = step_.out
#@queue

case $LOADL_STEP_NAME in
  step_1 )
    mpirun -exe my_app.x -mode VN -np 4 ;;
  step_2 )
    mpirun -exe my_app_2.x -mode VN -np 16 ;;
  step_3 )
    mpirun -exe my_app_3.x -mode VN -np 64 ;;
esac

```

This example contains three separate job steps: `step_1`, `step_2` and `step_3`. The second step, `step_2` depends on the first step `step_1` and will run only if `step_1` exits with the correct exit status. The last step, `step_3`, is independent of the rest of the job steps.

Note that all of the job steps use different executables. On the Blue Gene system each of the executables should be started with the `mpirun` command in order to be properly executed on the compute nodes. To control the execution of the steps the `$LOADL_STEP_NAME` variable may be used. Another way of identifying job steps is the `$(stepid)` variable in a job command file which contains the job step identifier and increases after each `queue` command.

7.6.2. Job command file variables

The Loadleveler system has furthermore variables that can be used in a job command file. The syntax for all Loadleveler variables is: `$(variable_name)`. The following list enumerates the most helpful available variables:

`$(home)`

The home directory of the user used to run the job.

`$(host)`

The hostname of the machine from which the job was submitted. Variables `$(host)` and `$(hostname)` are equivalent.

`$(jobid)`

The id number assigned to this job by LoadLeveler.

`$(stepid)`

The id number assigned to this job step when multiple job steps are defined.

`$(user)`

The user name of the user submitting the job.

7.6.3. Run-time environment variables

For a complete reference of the LoadLeveler run time environment variables please refer to the LoadLeveler manual.

7.7. Further reading, information and references

JUGENE documentation on the web

- Compiling and tuning applications [http://www.fz-juelich.de/sid_18A2A4DB9A988554330F1068A259BA08/ias/jsc/EN/Expertise/Supercomputers/JUGENE/UserInfo/CompilingTuning.html]

General related information

- IBM compiler documentation [http://publib.boulder.ibm.com/infocenter/comphelp/v111v131/index.jsp?topic=%2Fcom.ibm.xlf131.aix.doc%2Fcompiler_ref%2Fparlist.html]
- HDF group [<http://www.hdfgroup.org/HDF5/>]
- netCDF [<http://www.unidata.ucar.edu/software/netcdf/>]
- SIONlib [<http://www.fz-juelich.de/jsc/sionlib/>]

8. Debugging

If an application aborts unexpectedly it is useful to monitor the execution of the application in more detail in order to check which branches of the code are actually executed, what are the actual values of variables, which part of the memory is used etc. The simplest way to do this *debugging* is to use `print` statements in the code in order to get the desired information. However, this is tedious (each time a `print` or `write` statement is added the source needs to be recompiled and rerun). Furthermore, since the code is modified the runtime conditions change and may influence the behavior of the applications. Therefore, this way of debugging is not recommended.

Instead, in the first place the compiler offers the possibility to check for certain errors during the compilation of the code. For this special compiler flags have to be used which will be described in more detail in the next section. It is recommended to go this way first when debugging is necessary, because the usage is quite easy and does not require any additional software.

But not all errors can be detected this way since some occur only at run time. In this case *Debuggers* need to be employed. Debuggers are powerful tools to analyze the executions of applications *on the fly*, meaning while they are running. In general, the corresponding applications need to be recompiled once using appropriate compiler flags and are then executed under the control of the debugger.

8.1. Compiler flags

8.1.1. Debugging options of the compiler

In this section useful debugging options for the XL compilers are listed and explained. Simply add them to the compile command you usually use for your application. The information are taken from the man pages of the XL compilers, for further information about compiler flags just type `man bgx1f` or `man bgx1c`.

`-O0`

With this option all optimizations performed by the compiler are switched off. Sometimes errors can occur due to too aggressive compiler optimizations (rounding of floating point numbers, rearrangement of loops and/or operations etc.). If you encounter problems that might be connected to such issues (for example, wrong or inaccurate numeric results) try this option and check whether the problem persists. If not, increase moderately the optimization level. See Section 5.1.2 for further details.

`-qcheck[=<suboptions_list>]`

For Fortran this option is identical to the `-C` option (see list of flags for Fortran codes below). For C/C++ codes this option enables different runtime checks depending on the `suboptions_list` (colon-separated list, see below for suboptions) specified and raises a runtime exception (SIGTRAP signal) if a violation is encountered.

`all`

Enables all suboptions.

`bounds`

Performs runtime checking of addresses when subscripting within an object of known size.

`divzero`

Performs runtime checking of integer division. A trap will occur if an attempt is made to divide by zero.

`nullptr`

Performs runtime checking of addresses contained in pointer variables used to reference storage.

`-qflttrap[=<suboptions_list>]`

Generates instructions to detect and trap runtime floating-point exceptions. `<suboptions_list>` is a colon-separated list of one or more of the following suboptions:

`enable`

`imprecise`

Only checks for the specified exceptions on subprogram entry and exit.

`inexact`

Detects floating-point inexact exceptions.

`invalid`

Detects floating-point invalid operation exceptions.

`nanq`

Generates code to detect and trap NaNQ (Quiet Not-a-Number) exceptions handled or generated by floating-point operations.

`overflow`

Detects floating-point overflow.

`underflow`

Detects floating-point underflow.

`zerodivide`

Detects floating-point division by zero.

`-qhalt=<sev>`

Stops the compiler after the first phase if the severity level of errors detected equals or exceeds the specified level `<sev>`. The severity levels in increasing order of severity are:

`i` = informational messages

`l` = language-level messages (Fortran only)

`w` = warning messages

`e` = error messages

`s` = severe error messages

`u` = unrecoverable error messages (Fortran only)

`-qinitauto=[<hex_value>]`

Initializes each byte or word of storage for automatic variables to the specified hexadecimal value `<hex_value>`. This generates extra code and should only be used for error determination. If you specify `-qinitauto` without a `<hex_value>`, the compiler initializes the value of each byte of automatic storage to zero.

The following flags can be used only with *Fortran* codes

`-C`

Checks each reference to an array element, array section, or character substring for correctness. This way some array-bound violations can be detected.

`-qinit=f90ptr`

Makes the initial association status of pointers disassociated instead of undefined. This option applies to Fortran 90 and above. The default association status of pointers is undefined.

`-qsigtrap[=<trap_handler>]`

Sets up the specified trap handler to catch SIGTRAP exceptions when compiling a file that contains a main program. This option enables you to install a handler for SIGTRAP signals without calling the SIGNAL subprogram in the program.

The following flags apply only to C/C++ codes

`-qformat=[<options_list>]`

Warns of possible problems with string input and output format specifications. Functions diagnosed are `printf`, `scanf`, `strftime`, `strfmon` family functions and functions marked with format attributes. `<options_list>` is a comma-separated list of one or more of the following suboptions:

`all`

Turns on all format diagnostic messages.

`exarg`

Warns if excess arguments appear in `printf` and `scanf` style function calls.

`nlt`

Warns if a format string is not a string literal, unless the format function takes its format arguments as a `va_list`.

`sec`

Warns of possible security problems in use of format functions.

`y2k`

Warns of `strftime` formats that produce a 2-digit year.

`zln`

Warns of zero-length formats.

`-qinfo=[[<suboption>] [, <groups_list>]]`

Produces or suppresses additional informational messages. `<groups_list>` is a colon-separated list. If a `<groups_list>` is specified along with a `<suboption>`, a colon must separate them. The suboptions are:

`all`

Enables all diagnostic messages for all groups.

`private`

Lists shared variables that are made private to a parallel loop.

`reduction`

Lists variables that are recognized as reduction variables inside a parallel loop.

The list of groups that can be specified is extensive. Here only a few are given. For a complete list please refer to the manual page of the `bgx1c` compiler.

C code that might behave differently between C89 and C99 language levels

`cls`

C++ classes

`cmp`

Possible redundancies in unsigned comparisons

`cmd`

Possible redundancies or problems in conditional expressions

`gen`

General diagnostic messages

`ord`

Unspecified order of evaluation

`ppc`

Trace of preprocessor actions

`uni`

Uninitialized variables

8.1.2. Compiler flags for using debuggers

In order to run your code under the control of a debugger, you need to recompile your application including the following compiler flags (XL compilers):

```
-g -qfullpath
```

Additionally, the flag `-qkeepparm` may be useful. When specified, it ensures that function parameters are stored on the stack even if the application is optimized. As a result, parameters remain in the expected memory location, providing access to the values of these incoming parameters to debuggers.

8.2. Available debuggers

Once you have compiled your application with the correct compiler flags (Section 8.1.2) you can run your application under the control of a debugger and monitor the behavior on the fly in detail. We introduce the debuggers which are available on JUGENE in the following subsection.

8.2.1. DDT

The Distributed Debugging Tool (DDT) is a graphical debugger supporting C, C++, Fortran 77, and Fortran 90 programs. Among other features it offers:

- Multi-process and multi-threaded
- 1D + 2D array data visualization
- Support for MPI parallel debugging (automatic attach, message queues)
- Support for OpenMP (Version 2.x and later)

- Job submission from within debugger

8.2.1.1. Running DDT on JUGENE

Important

In order to be able to use the graphical user interface, please make sure you are logged in with

```
ssh -X
```

If you are not directly connected to JUGENE, make sure you are using for all ssh connections the `-X` option and that your local system (laptop, PC) has a running X server!

In order to debug your program load the `UNITE` and `ddt` modules first:

```
module load UNITE ddt
```

Then start the DDT debugger with

```
ddt
```

After clicking on the DDT logo a dialog box appears (Figure 14).

Figure 14. DDT welcome dialog box

Choose `Run and Debug a Program` and select (Figure 15) your application (after compilation with the appropriate flags Section 8.1.2) in the next dialog box, adjust the number of nodes and the OpenMP settings if applicable (for further options click on `Advanced`) and finally click on `Submit`.

Figure 15. DDT dialog box for choosing the executable and runtime parameters.

The application is submitted to the batch system and queued. Once the job is launched DDT will attach to the application, the DDT process window will appear (Figure 16) and you can start to debug your application. For further information about the DDT debugger and its capabilities please see the DDT documentation (Allinea Software) [<http://www.allinea.com/support/ddt-support>].

Figure 16. DDT process window.

8.2.2. TotalView

TotalView is a very powerful debugger supporting C, C++, Fortran 77, Fortran 90, PGI HPF and assembler programs and offers among others the following features:

- Multi-process and multi-threaded
- C++ support (templates, inheritance, inline functions)
- F90 support (user types, pointers, modules)
- 1D + 2D array data visualization
- Support for parallel debugging (MPI: automatic attach, message queues, OpenMP, pthreads)
- Scripting and batch debugging
- Memory debugging
- Reverse debugging with ReplayEngine

8.2.2.1. Using TotalView interactively

Important

In order to be able to use the graphical user interface please make sure you are logged in with

```
ssh -X
```

If you are not directly connected to JUGENE, make sure you are using for all ssh connections the `-X` option and that your local system (laptop, PC) has a running X server!

In order to debug your program with TotalView load the `UNITE` and `totalview` modules first:

```
module load UNITE totalview
```

The most common way to use TotalView (like any other debugger) is an interactive usage with a graphical user interface. In order to do so start your application (after compilation with the appropriate flags, Section 8.1.2) with `llrun` (Section 4.3.6) using the option `-tv`. For example:

```
llrun -np <ntasks> -mode VN -tv [-env OMP_NUM_THREADS=<nthreads>]  
application.x
```

This will start the program `application.x` with `<ntasks>` and `<nthreads>` per task in VN mode. If your application is a pure MPI code, you can omit the `-env` option.

After the corresponding partition is booted TotalView will launch three windows: the root window (Figure 19), the process window (Figure 18), and the startup-parameter window (Figure 17).

Figure 17. TotalView startup-parameters window

Figure 18. TotalView process window

In the startup-parameter window (Figure 17), you have the four tags `Debugging Options`, `Arguments`, `Standard I/O` and `Parallel`. If you wish to activate the memory debugging check the corresponding box in the tag `Debugging Options`. If you would like to change or add the arguments passed to your application or to `mpirun` you can do so under `Arguments`. Please *do not change* anything in `Parallel`. Once you have made all changes needed, click on `OK`.

Now click on `GO` in the process window of TotalView (Figure 18). TotalView will proceed executing the `mpirun` command and launch your application. This may take several minutes depending on the size of the partition you have requested (which is the number of tasks you would like to use).

Finally, a dialog box (Figure 20) appears. Click on `YES` and after a few seconds the source code of the main program of your application appears in the process window and you can start debugging your code.

Figure 20. A dialog window appears after clicking on GO

Since a detailed description of the usage of TotalView is far beyond the scope of this guide, please refer to the TotalView documentation (Rogue Wave Software) [<http://www.roguewave.com/support/product-documentation/totalview-family.aspx#totalview>] for a user's guide and further information about TotalView.

8.2.2.2. Using TotalView in batch mode

Sometimes using the interactive GUI for debugging is not straightforward, for example in cases where the error occurs after several hours of execution. In this case it would be very cumbersome to wait until the code has reached the corresponding spot.

In such cases TotalView can be executed in batch mode. Prepare a job command file (see Figure 20) and launch your application with `tvscript` instead of `mpirun`.

The general syntax for `tvscript` on JUGENE is

```
tvscript [options] -mpi BlueGene -np <ntasks> -starter_args "filename
[mpi-arguments] [-args program_args]" mpirun
```

Here [options] are `tvscript` options, filename is the name of the executable to debug (*must* be the first of the `starter_args`) and `-args` is followed by the arguments which are usually specified with the same option of the `mpirun` command. The last command *must* be `mpirun`.

Example 19 shows an example job command file using `tvscript` to debug an application.

Example 19. Job command script using `tvscript`

```

#@job_name          = tvscript_dbg
#@comment          = "batch debugging"
#@output           = tvscript_dbg.out
#@error            = tvscript_dbg.err
#@environment      = COPY_ALL
#@job_type         = bluegene
#@notification     = never
#@bg_size          = 32
#@wall_clock_limit = 00:30:00
#@queue

module load UNITE totalview

tvscript -create_actionpoint "function=>display_backtrace\
-show_arguments" -mpi BlueGene -np 4\
-starter_args "application.x -mode VN" mpirun

```

The executable to debug is `application.x` and should run with 4 tasks in VN mode. At the beginning of the function `function` an action point is created. When `tvscript` reaches that action point, it logs a backtrace and the method's arguments.

Running this job script, two log files are created by `tvscript`:

```
mpirun-<date>_<time>.slog
mpirun-<date>_<time>.log
```

The `slog` file (Summary Log File) contains a summary which events occurred. In the example above, this file contains four lines (one for each task):

```
Actionpoint function hit, performing action display_backtrace with \
options -show_arguments
Actionpoint function hit, performing action display_backtrace with \
options -show_arguments
Actionpoint function hit, performing action display_backtrace with \
options -show_arguments
Actionpoint function hit, performing action display_backtrace with \
options -show_arguments
```

This indicates that all tasks reached the defined action point and performed the corresponding action (show the arguments of the function `function`).

The `log` file contains more detailed information. In this case it lists (for each task) the names and values of the arguments of the function `function`.

For further information about `tvscript` and a complete list of options, please see the TotalView documentation [<http://www.roguewave.com/support/product-documentation/totalview-family.aspx#totalview>].

8.3. Analyzing core dumps

If an application aborts due to an error the current status of the memory usage of the application can be written to disk (*core dump files*) before the execution stops. Due to the fact that writing core files from thousands of nodes takes (too) much time, the generating of core files is suppressed. However, you can enable the generation of core dumps exporting the environment variable `BG_COREDUMPDISABLED` to 0 in your job command file:

```
mpirun -env BG_COREDUMPDISABLED=0 <other mpirun options>
application.x
```

where `application.x` is your application. Please use the `-g` option when compiling your application in case you would like to analyze core dump files.

Important

Use this option with care, because a core dump file *for each process* is generated. Running with 16000 MPI tasks means that 16000 core files are generated! Before using this option try to reproduce the error with the least number of tasks possible! Alternatively, you can limit the number of core files using `setrlimit(RLIMIT_CORE)`. In this case you need to modify your source code. See the manual page of `setrlimit` (`man setrlimit`) for further information.

8.3.1. Core dump file analysis using `addr2line`

Core dump files are plain text files that include traceback information in hexadecimal. To read and convert the hexadecimal addresses the tool `addr2line` can be used. Assuming your application is

called `application.x` you can convert a hexadecimal address `<hexaddr>` from the core dump file to readable text in the following way:

```
addr2line -e application.x <hexaddr>
```

For further information about `addr2line` please use

```
man addr2line
addr2line -h
```

8.3.2. Core dump file analysis using debuggers

Core dump files can be also analyzed using the DDT (Section 8.2.1) or the TotalView debugger (Section 8.2.2).

8.3.2.1. DDT

To debug using core dump files, start DDT as described in Section 8.2.1. Then click the `Open Core Files` button on the welcome screen (Figure 14). This opens the `Open Core Files` window, which allows you to select an executable and a set of core dump files. Click `OK` to open the core dump files and start debugging them. While DDT is in this mode, you cannot play, pause or step (because there is no process active). You are, however, able to evaluate expressions and browse the variables and stack frames saved in the core dump files. The `End Session` menu option will return DDT to its normal mode of operation.

8.3.2.2. TotalView

Start TotalView as described in Section 8.2.2.1. After the source code of your application appears in the process window, go to the menu `File` and select `New Program`. Select `Open a core file` in the dialog box which appears and choose a core dump file. The `Process` window displays the core dump file, with the `Stack Trace`, `Stack Frame`, and `Source Panes` showing the state of the process when it dumped core. The title bar of the `Process Window` names the signal that caused the core dump. The right arrow in the line number area of the `Source Pane` indicates the value of the program counter (PC) when the process encountered the error.

8.4. Further reading, information and references

JUGENE documentation on the web

- Brief DDT description (JSC). [<http://apps.fz-juelich.de/unite/index.php/Ddt>]
- Brief TotalView description (JSC). [<http://apps.fz-juelich.de/unite/index.php/Totalview>]

General related information

- DDT documentation (Allinea Software) [<http://www.allinea.com/support/ddt-support>]
- TotalView documentation (Rogue Wave Software) [<http://www.roguewave.com/support/product-documentation/totalview-family.aspx#totalview>]

Bibliographic references

[RedBook AD] Carlos Sosa and Brant Knudson. *IBM System Blue Gene Solution: Blue Gene/P Application Development*. 4th edition. 11 September 2009. Copyright © 2007, 2009 International Business Machines Corporation.